

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D5.4. Report on best cropping systems and management practices that enhance soil biodiversity and the associated ecosystem services

Universidade de Vigo

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Summary

This deliverable D5.4 combines the results of deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 to develop and present recommendations for agricultural practice as an outcome of the different 15 case studies. They were conducted across 17 different field sites - including commercial farms and experimental plots dedicated to wheat, potatoes, and vegetables - and were established in six different European pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral, Boreal. Besides the location of each case study, the implemented management practices are presented. For each case study, strategies to promote soil biodiversity and their main benefits are recommended. Potential drawbacks are mentioned as far as known.

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INTRODUCTION: MEANING AND AIM OF CASE STUDIES IN SOILDIVERAGRO

Fifteen case studies, conducted across 17 different field sites—including commercial farms and experimental plots dedicated to wheat, potatoes, and vegetables—were established in six different European pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral, and Boreal. These studies aimed to evaluate the effects of innovative management practices and cropping systems on soil biological diversity, with a focus on key groups such as prokaryotes (archaea and bacteria), fungi, nematodes, and earthworms. Furthermore, the overall performance of European agriculture was assessed through parameters related to crop quality—including growth, yield, nutritional value, and pest incidence—as well as soil quality indicators such as pH, nutrient content, soil structure, and the presence of pesticides.

Two case studies (CS1 and CS2) were conducted in the Mediterranean South region (Region of Murcia, Southeast Spain) to study the effects of different mineral and organic fertilization strategies, with and without bacterial and/or fungal inoculants (biostimulants). On the one hand, the experimental farm selected in CS1 was located in an agricultural area dedicated to intensive horticulture. The objective of this study was to investigate the potential of biostimulants as a partial replacement for mineral fertilizers to improve soil health and crop yield. During the three years of experimentation, the crop rotation included potato, broccoli, melon, and potato. Four different fertilization treatments were designed under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization, where mineral fertilizer was reduced by 30–50% and partially replaced by biostimulants (growth-promoting bacteria and fungi). On the other hand, in CS2, a commercial farm primarily dedicated to cereal cultivation was selected. The main objective of this case study was to apply novel strategies based on crop rotations and biostimulant-based formulations to increase nutrient availability and water retention, reduce the incidence of soilborne crop diseases, and enhance grain production. Following local practices, the crops (rye, wheat, and ervil) were cultivated under organic, rainfed management. Four different fertilization treatments were applied, reducing the organic fertilizer (by 30%—pig slurry and compost) and partially replacing it with biostimulants (nutrient-solubilizing bacteria and fungi).

Three case studies (CS3, CS4, and CS5), located in the autonomous community of Galicia (northwestern Spain), within the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region, were established to test various agricultural management practices to address persistent agronomic challenges in the area. In this region, potatoes represent the main crop, typically rotated with cereals such as wheat. Among the primary issues identified are the excessive use of agricultural inputs, leading to soil and water contamination; a high incidence of pests and diseases; and low levels of both aboveground and belowground biodiversity. Taking this into account, Case Study 3 explores the potential of crop diversification to increase soil biodiversity and, together with the management of trap crops in potato fields, to reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes. This strategy aims to increase soil biodiversity and reduce the use of nematicides, thereby promoting sustainable and profitable potato production practices. On the other hand, Case Study 4 examines the application of mycorrhizal fungi in potato cultivation as a means to mitigate the prevalence of common scab, reduce dependency on phosphorus-based fertilizers, and simultaneously improve both crop yield and soil biodiversity.

Finally, Case Study 5 investigates the implementation of a pest alert system aimed at reducing fungicide applications and minimizing the use of heavy agricultural machinery in the field.

Four case studies (CS6, CS7, CS8, and CS9), located in Belgium within the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, were organized based on responses to a questionnaire and feedback collected during regional meetings with stakeholders and end-users. The gathered information identified and prioritized the main threats affecting agro-ecosystems in Flanders (Belgium): the use of chemical fertilizers and liquid manure continues to cause excessive nitrate and phosphate leaching into surface water and groundwater; intensive management practices lead to a deficit in soil organic matter; and a general decline in soil health, marked by degraded biological and structural conditions, which further contributes to issues such as soil erosion and water scarcity. To address these agricultural challenges, each case study focused on specific aspects of soil fertility, organic matter content, and biodiversity in distinct ways. Case Study 6 evaluated the combined effects of applying farmyard manure, with or without co-composting using 'brown' material, alongside different cover crop management strategies (e.g., incorporation or mowing). Case Study 7 assessed the impact of species-diverse cover crop mixtures, ranging from simple combinations to mixes with up to 12 species, in order to further diversify cropping systems. Case Study 8 compared agricultural systems (intensive versus extensive, conventional versus organic), while Case Study 9 examined the use of various organic fertilization sources, such as farmyard manure, compost, and fermented grass-clover silage.

It is important to note that the results were likely influenced by the climatic conditions in Belgium during the growing seasons from 2019 to 2023. These years were characterized by generally very warm weather and, at times, exceptionally dry conditions (Table 1). Specifically: **2019**: Warm, sunny, and relatively dry.

TABLE 1

YEAR	MT (°C)	MMAT (°C)	MMIT (°C)	TH (DAYS)	TP (MM)	PN (DAYS)	SS (HOURS)
2019	11,5	15,5	7,8	11	798,6	182	1757
2020	12,2	16,1	8,1	12	731,9	169	1838
2021	10,7	14,3	7,2	0	1038,8	192	1590
2022	12,2	16,3	8,1	13	701,4	148	1974
2023	12,1	15,8	8,6	11	837,1	190	1603

Table 1. Climatological conditions in Belgium during the experimental period of case-study 6. MT: mean temperature; MMAT: mean maximum temperature; MMIT: mean minimum temperature; TH: tropical heat; TP: tropical precipitation; PN: number of precipitation days; SS: sunshine.

- **2020:** Very hot, sunny, and dry.
- **2021:** Exceptionally wet.
- **2022:** Very hot, sunny, and dry, with an extremely low number of rainy days.
- **2023:** Also very hot and wet.

The mean temperatures in 2020 and 2022 were the highest recorded since 1991. Notably, 2022 had the highest mean maximum temperature, while 2023 recorded the highest mean minimum temperature during this period.

In the Continental pedoclimatic region within Germany, three case studies were established (CS10a, CS10b, and CS11). The aim was to promote beneficial soil organisms by new and innovative agricultural measures to increase soil intrinsic self-regulation against soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi (e.g. *Fusarium* and their mycotoxins).

Case study 12 (CS12), located in Estonia within the Nemoral pedoclimatic zone, was partially designed based on data collected through stakeholder questionnaires and feedback provided during regional workshops involving end-users and local actors. The selection process was further guided by regional demands for evidence-based knowledge concerning the effects of soil management practices on soil properties. Informed by both stakeholder input and regional agronomic priorities, a range of agricultural management strategies was identified to enhance agroecosystem resilience, maintain soil quality, and promote soil biodiversity within Estonian farming systems. With respect to pesticide application, the presence of pesticide residues and their effects on soil biota—specifically assessed through the use of earthworms as bioindicators—was evaluated under direct seeding and reduced tillage conditions. Additionally, the impact of soil management practices was investigated across various farming systems, including conventional agriculture with conventional tillage, conventional farming under no-till practices, and organic farming under no-till regimes.

Four case studies (CS13, CS14a, CS14b, and CS15) located in Finland, within the Boreal pedoclimatic region, were organised based on responses to a questionnaire and feedback gathered during regional meetings with stakeholders and end-users. Based on the collected information we identified agricultural management practices which could promote overall resilience and soil diversity of agroecosystems in Finland: the use of reduced or minimum tillage with or without direct sowing to minimize the negative impacts of deep-ploughing to promote soil health and biological diversity of soil, and use of catch crops and organic amendments from recycled forest-derived material to prevent nutrient and carbon loss from early potato fields with short cultivation period. Case Study 13 explores the effects of forest-derived recycled organic amendments from side-streams of the pulp mill spread in the early potato field after the harvesting. Case Study 14a investigates the impact of springtime ploughing in cereal (spring wheat) field under long-term organic farming with minimum tillage. Case Study 14b investigates the impact of autumntime ploughing in cereal (winter wheat) field under long-term organic farming with reduced tillage combined with direct sowing. Case Study 15 examines the impact of two different catch crops, Phacelia and rye (*Secale cereale*) in the early potato field sown in the field after the harvest.

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The data obtained from the case studies will support the analysis of environmental and economic impacts at both farm and regional levels. Ultimately, this will enable the identification and selection of the most effective crop diversification methods (including cover crops), organic fertilizers, and farming systems to improve the functionality of soil macro- and microorganisms, which are crucial for enhancing soil health, crop productivity, and other ecosystem services.

This report highlights the specific characteristics of each case study, focusing on their strategies for implementing management practices that promote soil biodiversity, as well as the key benefits and potential drawbacks of these approaches.

CASE STUDY 1: USE OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY TO REDUCE SOIL-BORNE DISEASES/PESTS INCIDENCE AND INCREASE NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY IN POTATOES CROPPED IN MULTIPLE CROPPING AND ROTATIONS

Location

Case Study 1(CS1) was carried out in Cartagena, Southeast of Spain, at the Tomás Ferro Experimental Farm of the Polytechnic University of Cartagena (UPCT), Spain (37°41'16.6"N 0°56'55.6"W) (Fig. 1.1). The climate is semiarid Mediterranean with a mean annual precipitation of 300 mm and a mean annual temperature of 18 °C. Annual potential evapotranspiration surpasses 1.200 mm. Soil is classified as Haplic Calcisol (loamic, hypercalcic) [IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022], with clay loam texture, organic matter content of 1.8 %, CaCO₃ of 25.2%, and a pH of 8.2. The experimental farm is located in a region dedicated to intensive horticulture, with adoption of multiple cropping (winter and summer crops) to increase profitability, and rotations, to avoid problems of monocropping. Main crops are lettuce, cabbage, spinach, broccoli, celery, melon, watermelon, and potato. The most important environmental problems are low below and aboveground biodiversity, soil erosion, low soil organic matter content, weak soil structure, low availability of nutrients, and excessive use of water and nutrients.

Fig. 1.1. Location of Case Study 1 (CS1).

Management practices implemented in the case study

During the three years of experimentation, we rotated in Case Study 1 the following crops (Fig. 1.2):

- 1) Potato, from 22 December 2020 to 4 June 2021.
- 2) Broccoli, from 5 October 2021 to 10 January 2022.
- 3) Melon, from 29 March 2022 to 14 July 2022.
- 4) Potato, from 16 December 2022 to 15 May 2023.

Fig. 1.2. Rotation implemented in Case Study 1.

Following the local practices, the crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, where we reduced mineral fertilizer to partially replace it by biostimulants:

- 1) Inorganic fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (**F100**).
- 2) The 50% of the rate of inorganic fertilizers added in F100 (**F50**).
- 3) F50 + the application of a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (**BAI**).
- 4) F50 + the application of a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (**BAI+FU**).

The formulation of BAI was mostly based on plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) such as *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Bacillus* (Bactoneco®). The formulation of BAI+FU was mostly based on a mix of PGPR and beneficial fungi as *Bacillus*, *Azotobacter*, and non-mycorrhizal fungi (Nuve®). These products were provided by "Fertilizantes y Nutrientes Ecológicos S.L." (Spain), and the exact compositions were not shared due to the protection of the providers' intellectual property rights.

The field experiment was established as a completely randomized design with four treatments of 740 m², each composed of four replicates. All treatments received the same quantity of irrigation, that was scheduled according to the climatic conditions, crop coefficient, and evapotranspiration rate. In all treatments, the soil was tilled at 25 cm depth for the preparation of the crop.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

- The addition of biostimulants did not increase crop yields in any crops, but kept yields at the same level of full inorganic fertilization.
- The addition of biostimulants did not affect broccoli and melon quality. However, it improved potato quality. Although size distribution and starch content showed no significant differences between treatments, BAI+FU showed the highest mean weight and flesh firmness of tubers. In addition, the addition of BAI+FU reduced the incidence of *Rhizoctonia* in tubers compared to full inorganic fertilization by 30%, improving the marketable value of the potatoes.
- Soil CO₂ emissions were reduced by 40% when adding biostimulants compared to full inorganic fertilization.
- The application of biofertilizers enhanced N fixation, ammonification, denitrification, and CO₂ fixation, compared to full inorganic fertilization.
- There was an increase in prokaryote diversity with the addition of biostimulants, with changes in the taxonomic composition. However, the use of biostimulants did not affect overall fungal diversity and composition. There was a decrease in the abundance of fungal pathogens and an increase in the relative abundance of fungal symbiotrophs in BAI+FU.
- The number and biodiversity of nematodes was not affected by the addition of biostimulants, but their composition changed compared to full inorganic fertilisation. In addition, biostimulants addition led to decreased functional complexity of the nematode community, increasing nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi.
- There was no clear effect of soil physical and chemical properties shaping the prokaryotic, fungal or nematode communities.

In conclusion, the addition of biostimulants, mostly when plant growth promoted bacteria and fungi were added together (BAI+FU), was positive to keep high crop yields and reduce soil CO₂ emissions. For potatoes, the addition of biostimulants also improved potato quality, and reduced the incidence of pathogens in the tubers, increasing their marketable value. Furthermore, biofertilizers increased soil bacterial diversity and changed bacterial composition, with increased soil functioning, and increases in fungal symbiotrophs abundance.

Thus, the use of biostimulants can be fostered in Mediterranean horticulture to reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers, with stimulation of beneficial microorganisms that contributes to keep high crop yields and reduce soil pathogens abundance and incidence.

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Potential drawbacks

No drawbacks observed in this case study with the addition of both biostimulants, with no negative effects compared to full inorganic fertilization.

References

IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

CASE STUDY 2: USE OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY TO INCREASE NUTRIENT AND WATER AVAILABILITY AND REDUCE SOIL-BORNE DISEASES INCIDENCE TO INCREASE WHEAT YIELDS

Location

Case Study 2 (CS2) was carried out in the farm La Junquera, Region of Murcia (Southeast of Spain) 37° 56'11.2" N 2° 10'11.2" W (Fig. 2.1). The climate is semiarid Mediterranean with a mean annual precipitation of 316 mm and a mean annual temperature of 13 °C. Annual potential evapotranspiration surpasses 1.000 mm. Soil is classified as Calcic Cambisol [IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022], with clay texture, organic matter content of 2.3 %, CaCO₃ of 49%, and a pH of 9.0. The commercial farm is located in a region dedicated to field crops, mostly cereals such as wheat, barley or rye, with adoption of rotations to avoid problems of monocropping. The most important environmental problems are low below and aboveground biodiversity, soil erosion, low soil organic matter content, weak soil structure, and low availability of nutrients and water.

Fig. 2.1. Location of Case Study 2.

Management practices implemented in the case study

During the three years of experimentation, we rotated in Case Study 2 the following crops (Fig. 2.2):

- 1) Rye, from 12 December 2020 to 29 July 2021.
- 2) Wheat, from 1 December 2021 to 3 August 2022.
- 3) Ervil, sown on 1 December 2022, but crop could not develop owing to extreme draught during winter/spring 2023.

Fig. 2.2. Rotation implemented in Case Study 2.

Following the local practices, the crops were established under organic rainfed management. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, where we reduced organic fertilizer to partially replace it by biostimulants:

- 1) Organic fertilizers (pig slurry and compost) applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (**F100**).
- 2) The 50% of the rate of organic fertilizers added in F100 (**F50**).
- 3) F50 + the application of a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (**BAI**).
- 4) F50 + the application of a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (**BAI+FU**).

The formulation of BAI was mostly based on plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) such as *Azospirillum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Bacillus* (Bactoneco®). The formulation of BAI+FU was mostly based on a mix of PGPR and beneficial fungi as *Bacillus*, *Azotobacter*, and non-mycorrhizal fungi (Nuve®). These products were provided by "Fertilizantes y Nutrientes Ecológicos S.L." (Spain), and the exact compositions were not shared due to the protection of the providers' intellectual property rights.

The field experiment was established in one block with the four treatments of 1.1 ha each. True field replication was impossible owing to machinery and labour constraints in the commercial farm. In all treatments, the soil was tilled at 25 cm depth for the preparation of the crop.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

- The addition of biostimulants did not increase crop yields in any crops, but kept yields at the same level of full inorganic fertilization. Crop quality was not affected by the addition of biostimulants.
- There was no effect of biostimulants in prokaryotic, fungal and nematode diversity and composition. Functional gene abundance for genes involved in C and N cycles were not affected by biostimulants either. However, biostimulants addition led to decreased functional complexity of the nematode community, increasing nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi. In addition, the 50% reduction in organic fertilisation (F50) increased nematode diversity.

In conclusion, organic fertilisation could be reduced for cereal production under organic rainfed management with no negative effect on crop yield and quality, and soil properties. The use of biofertilizers was not successful to increase productivity neither soil biodiversity nor multifunctionality.

Potential drawbacks

Owing to the high price of commercial biostimulants, this strategy may not be competitive for rainfed organic systems under Mediterranean climate, since there is no increase in crop yields and quality.

References

IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

CASE STUDY 3: USE OF CROP DIVERSIFICATION AND TRAP CROPS IN POTATO FIELDS TO REDUCE THE INCIDENCE OF CYST NEMATODE, REDUCE NEMATICIDES AND INCREASE YIELD AND SOIL BIODIVERSITY

Location

Case Study 3 (CS3) was implemented in the Lusitanian Pedoclimatic region, Spain. Concretely in the town of Sandiás, Ourense province, Galicia region (Fig. 3.1). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots used for this CS are 42° 6' 0.32" N, 7° 43' 29.98" W. This location has a mean annual temperature of 12.9 °C, mean annual precipitation of 780 mm and annual potential evapotranspiration of 2.9 mm.

Fig. 3.1. CS3 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

Management practices implemented in the case study

This case study was carried out in an experimental potato cropland of 5 ha, where potato is the main crop conventionally rotated with cereals (wheat). This area has high incidence of cyst nematode and low yield. Consequently, the use of nematicides is high, increasing costs production and contributing to soil and water pollution. In addition, aboveground and belowground biodiversity is low, mainly due to the high input's application.

New management practices implemented in this area were the **diversification of crop rotations** and introduction a **trap crop**. They were carried out between 2021 and 2023. The aims were to reduce the incidence of cyst nematode and consequently, decrease the nematicide inputs and N external fertilization, as well as increase crop yields and soil biodiversity (Fig. 3.2).

Fig. 3.2. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued.

To this, three different crop rotations were carried out (Table 3.1):

- 1) Control with conventional rotation (**Ctrl**).
- 2) Crop diversification, including a leguminous in the rotation to fix N in soil and reduce inputs application (**Alt1Pot**, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field).
- 3) Trap crop inclusion in the rotation, to reduce parasitic nematodes and thus, the use of nematicides (**Alt2Pot**, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field).

Table 3.1. Composition of each type of rotation including the period of application.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
Ctrl	Potatos	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos
	MAY – SEP 21	OCT 21 – JUL 22	MAY – SEP 23
Alt1Pot	Cereal (wheat)	Leguminous (peas)	Potatos
	ABR – JUL 21	ABR – JUL 22	MAY – SEP 23
Alt2Pot	Potatos	Trap crop	Potatos
	MAY – SEP 21	ABR – JUL 22	MAY – SEP 23

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The alternative crop rotation 2 (Alt2Pot) slightly increased in Proteobacteria, with a corresponding reduction in Acidobacteria compared to the control and Alt1Pot treatment. This indicates the trap crop produced an improvement in the nitrogen cycle, decomposition of organic matter, promotion of plant growth, greater biodiversity, and potential for bioremediation enhanced by an increase in Proteobacteria. Conversely, a reduction in Acidobacteria could indicate less competition for nutrients and a shift toward more fertile, nutrient-rich soils. **Overall, these results would generally benefit soil health and productivity, promoting a more active and efficient microbial ecosystem in terms of nutrient recycling.**

The rotation of Alt2Pot resulted in a significantly increased number of observed amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) compared to the alternative crop rotation 1 treatment. However, the increased number of observed ASVs in the Alt2Pot treatment did not significantly differ from the conventional control treatment. An increase in the number of observed ASV is typically indicative of greater species richness and potentially higher diversity. **Therefore, the best rotation to choose to increase soil biodiversity is the one including the trap crop.**

On the other side, the alternative crop rotation 1 system (rotation with legumes), presented an increased trend of genes involved in the carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles, except for the genes involved in nitrification, while the opposite trend was observed for samples from the alternative crop rotation 2 system (Alt2Pot), i.e., **the introduction of trap crops reduced the abundance of microorganisms involved in the carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles.**

In the same way, regarding fungal diversity, there was an increasing trend in the abundance of Nectriaceae and a decreasing trend in the abundance of Plectosphaerellaceae in Alt1Pot treatment. The most abundant genera of these families, *Gibberella* and *Gibellulopsis* contain common plant pathogens and might have different response to Alt1Pot treatment. There was also an increasing trend in the abundance of Hydnodontaceae in Alt2Pot. The most abundant genus of Hydnodontaceae, *Trechispora*, contains wood saprotrophs that might have benefited Alt2Pot treatment. **Therefore, the rotation including leguminous increased microbial pathogens while the rotation including the trap crop increased the presence of wood saprotrophs while decreasing the relative abundance of the pathogens.**

Regarding microbial characterization, none of the alternative treatments tested (Alt1Pot, Alt2Pot) increased neither microbial abundance nor any specific groups, compared to the Ctrl. Therefore, **alternative treatments did not alter microbial abundance maintaining their functional groups overall.**

Regarding nematodes abundance, with the alternative crop rotation 1 system (rotation with legumes), the number of nematodes dropped drastically in the last year of study while in the other treatment (trap crop inclusion) and control, the number of nematodes were maintained or increased moderately. Nematodes diversity showed that the predominant genera were Acrobelloides, Aphelenchoides, Cruznema and Aphelenchus. At the start, also Panagrolaimus is present in treatments "Alt1Pot" and "Ctrl". However, this genus is not highly represented in treatment "Alt2Pot". Acrobelloides, Aphelenchoides and Pristionchus are the predominantly genera present in the nematode communities together with Paratylenchus but, considering Paratylenchus is a plant-parasitic nematode genus capable of causing yield loss, **the treatment Alt2Pot tested in order to reduce plant parasitic-nematodes (PPN) was a success to reduce nematodes affecting main crop.** The analysis of nematode functional diversity showed that the "Ctrl" and "Alt2Pot" treatment show a significant increase concerning functional biodiversity. The same trend was observed with the treatment "Alt1Pot", although not statistically significant. Alternative crop rotations were investigated in this case-study and more complex crop rotations can induce a higher nematode community complexity. As a summary, **the treatments tested in this case study did not significantly increase functional biodiversity compared to the control, but they were maintained.** Additionally, and most important, **the treatment "Alt2Pot" tested mainly to reduce PPN, worked successfully by reducing their abundance.**

Finally, incorporating a trap crop (as in the Alt2Pot treatment) into the rotation system is recommended to reduce plant parasitic nematodes, promote soil biodiversity and a more active and efficient microbial ecosystem in terms of nutrient recycling. In contrast, crop rotations with legumes (Alt1Pot) changed the most abundant microbial pathogens' families and increased the abundance of genes driven carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles.

Therefore, taking into account all the results, **this strategy results in several key benefits:**

- 1) Enhanced nitrogen cycle and organic matter decomposition promoted by an increase Proteobacteria, which supports nutrient availability and plant growth.
- 2) Higher species richness and biodiversity indicated by the significant rise in observed amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) suggests greater microbial richness, which is crucial for a resilient and diverse soil ecosystem.
- 3) Reduced soil pathogens by decreasing fungi such as the Nectriaceae family and nematodes such as Paratylenchus genera, while promoting beneficial fungi like wood saprotrophs (e.g., Trechispora), will enhance nutrient cycling and productivity.

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Potential drawbacks

Since the impact of alternative crop rotation on fungi were either neutral or positive, potential drawbacks of them cannot be identified.

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CASE STUDY 4: USE OF MYCORRHIZA IN POTATO FIELDS TO REDUCE THE INCIDENCE OF COMMON SCAB, DECREASE THE USE OF PHOSPHORUS FERTILIZERS, INCREASE CROP YIELDS AND SOIL BIODIVERSITY

Location

Case Study 4 (CS4) was implemented in the Lusitanian Pedoclimatic region, Spain. Concretely in the town of Xinzo de Limia, Ourense province, Galicia region (Fig. 4.1). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots used for this CS are 42° 5' 37.09" N, 7° 41' 52.92" W. This location has a mean annual temperature of 12.9 °C, mean annual precipitation of 780 mm and annual potential evapotranspiration of 2.9 mm.

Fig. 4.1. Case Study 4 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

Management practices implemented in the case study

This case study was carried out in an experimental potato cropland of 9.6 ha, where potato is the main crop conventionally rotated with cereals (wheat). This area has high incidence of the common scab in potato crop and low yield. Consequently, potatoes are low valued and their profitability decreases. At the same time, the strategy followed to control common scab consist of maintaining soil at low pH (<5). Consequently, phosphorous availability decreases leading farmers to apply external P-fertilizers. This increases the production costs and reduces profitability as well as contributing to soil and water pollution and the reduction of soil biodiversity.

New management practices implemented in this area were **introducing mycorrhizas** and the **reduction of P doses**. They were carried out between 2021 and 2023. The aims were to reduce the

incidence of common scab and consequently, increase the potatoes value, and to slightly increase soil pH to increase P availability reducing the external P fertilization, while increasing crop yield and soil biodiversity (Fig. 4.2).

Fig. 4.2. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued at Case Study 4.

To this, five treatments were carried out (Table 4.1):

- 1) Control with conventional rotation.
- 2) Introduction of mycorrhiza in potato cycles and reduction the P fertilization to the half ($\frac{1}{2}$ P-dose).
- 3) Introduction of mycorrhiza in potato cycles and no application of P fertilization (No P).
- 4) Conventional rotation with reduction the P fertilization to the half ($\frac{1}{2}$ P-dose), without mycorrhiza.
- 5) Conventional rotation without the application of P (No P) fertilization and without mycorrhiza.

Table 4.1. Composition of each type of rotation including the period of application.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
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CONTROL (Ctrl)	Potatos	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos
MYCORRHIZA + ½ P (MycPotHP)	Potatos+mycorrhiza+½ P	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos + mycorrhiza + ½ P
MYCORRHIZA + NO P (MycNoP)	Potatos+mycorrhiza+no P	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos + mycorrhiza + No P
NO MYCORRHIZA + ½ P (PotHP)	Potatos + ½ P	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos + ½ P
NO MYCORRHIZA + NO P (PotNoP)	Potatos (No P)	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos (No P)

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

- Treatment with mycorrhizal inoculum without P fertilization (**MycNoP**) can **improve the abundance and diversity** of the prokaryotic community.
- **Reduced amount of phosphorus** in fertilization with or without mycorrhizal inoculant may change soil fungal community and thus **can be used to improve nutrient balance and water retention, decrease soil erosion**, and improve the **C sequestration capacity**.
- The incorporation of **mycorrhizal inoculum** can lead to an **increase in the abundance of microbial biomass**.
- The treatment **PotHP** caused a decrease in the Structure Index in terms of nematode diversity, which implies an increase in the imbalance between the different genera, leading to a **loss of biodiversity**.
- The treatment **MycNoP** resulted in an increase in the contents of exchangeable Mg, CaCO₃ and nitrates, thus **improving soil fertility**.
- The **PotHP** treatment (No mycorrhiza + ½ P) caused an increase in soil organic matter, as well as in the contents of exchangeable Mg and nitrates, while at the same time it led to a decrease in bioavailable Cu. Therefore, this treatment **increases C sequestration, improves soil fertility and decreases the possible toxic effects of Cu**.
- The **MycPotHP** treatment (Mycorrhiza + ½ P) resulted in an increase in ammonium and eCEC, thus **improving soil fertility**, while also causing a decrease in certain heavy metals, such as Fe or Zn.

- Finally, regarding earthworms, **the MycNoP, PotHP, and MycPotHP treatments resulted in a decrease in earthworm richness**, as earthworm richness was negatively correlated with POC, NH₄, FMa, NO₃, and Pav.

In conclusion, reduced phosphorus application, with or without mycorrhizal fungi, can enhance soil fertility, improve nutrient balance and water retention, reduce soil erosion, and increase carbon sequestration capacity. Additionally, the mycorrhizal treatment generally resulted in an increase in biodiversity, except for earthworms.

Potential drawbacks

Since the impacts of fertilization treatment with less phosphorus has clear positive impact on beneficial fungi, potential drawbacks of alternative phosphorus fertilization treatment in potato field in Lusitanian region cannot be identified.

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CASE STUDY 5: IMPLEMENTATION OF A PEST ALERT SYSTEM TO REDUCE THE USE OF FUNGICIDES IN POTATO AND WHEAT CROPS AND THEIR IMPACT ON BIODIVERSITY

Location

Case Study 5 (CS5) was implemented in the Lusitanian Pedoclimatic region, Spain. Concretely in the town of Sandiás, Ourense province, Galicia region (Fig. 5.1). The geographical coordinates of the experimental plots used for this case study are 42° 6' 3.92" N, 7° 43' 32.42" W. This location has a mean annual temperature of 12.9 °C, mean annual precipitation of 780 mm and annual potential evapotranspiration of 2.9 mm.

Fig. 5.1. Case Study 5 location (to the left) and experimental plot (to the right).

Management practices implemented in the case study

This case study was carried out in an experimental potato cropland of 0.75 ha, where potato is the main crop conventionally rotated with cereals (wheat). Potato crop in this area has high incidence of fungal diseases. High fungicide inputs are widely applied using heavy machinery. Consequently, soil is highly compacted, and the application of fungicides makes potatoes production costs increases. In addition, the high application of inputs contributes to soil and water pollution and the reduction of soil biodiversity.

New management practices implemented in this area were the **introduction of a pest alert system** (Fig. 5.2). This will provide an alert to the farmers when the concentration of fungi in the air is high, and the application of fungicides should be done. This system is expected to reduce the application

of fungicides as well as the reduction of heavy machinery in the field. The experiments were carried out between 2021 and 2023. In addition, it was aimed to increase crop yield and soil biodiversity (Fig. 5.3).

Fig. 5.2. Implementation of a decision support system at Case Study 5 (CS5).

Fig. 5.3. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued at Case Study 5.

To this, three treatments were carried out (Table 1):

- 1) Pest alert system control in potato (**DSSI**).
- 2) Conventional fungicide application in potato as control (**ConvPotFa- Control**).
- 3) Potato without fungicide application (**PotNoFA**).

Table 1. Composition of each type of rotation including the period of application.

Crop rotation	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3
ALERT SYSTEM (DSS)	Potatos	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos
CONVENTIONAL FUNGICIDE APPLICATION (ConvPotFa- Control)	Potatos	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos
NO FUNGICIDE (PotNoFA)	Potatos	Cereal (wheat)	Potatos
	MAY 21 – SEP 21	OCT 21 – JUL 22 → Fallow	MAY 23 – SEP 23

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

- The **PotNoFa** treatment (no fungicide application) resulted in an **increase in exchangeable cations contents, as well as elevated levels of NH₄ and NO₃**, while causing a decrease in CaCO₃ contents, compared to the **ConvPotFa** treatment (conventional fungicide application).
- The **Alert System (Ctrl)** treatment induced an **increase in total organic carbon (TOC) content, exchangeable cations and NH₄ levels**, while causing a reduction in NO₃ levels, compared to the ConvPotFa treatment (conventional fungicide application).
- Regarding prokaryotes, the **PotNoFa** treatment (no fungicide application) caused a pronounced reduction in Proteobacteria and Acidobacteria, while **promoting an enrichment of Firmicutes and Chloroflexi**, relative to the control treatment.
- In general, fungal richness was lower in the absence of fungicides. However, the use or non-use of fungicides did not seem to have a significant impact on the overall composition of the soil fungal community.
- Regarding nematodes, both the **PotNoFa** treatment (no fungicide application) and the **Alert System treatment (DSS)** showed an increase in nematode biodiversity, compared to the application of conventional fungicides (ConvPotFa).

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- Finally, regarding earthworms, the **Alert System treatment (DSS)** resulted in a decrease in earthworm richness.

In conclusion, the absence or reduced use of fungicides generally resulted in an improvement in soil fertility, characterized by a higher organic carbon and NH₄ content. Furthermore, the reduced or absent use of fungicides also contributed to an increase in nematode biodiversity.

Potential drawbacks

Quite expectedly, it seems that if fungicides are not used, fungal pathogens harmful for plants may benefit. However, it also seems that arise of pathogens could be minimized or avoided by paying attention to soil conditions affecting soil pH and other factors affecting nutrient balances (essential base cations) in soil.

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CASE STUDY 6: SOIL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE SOIL QUALITY WHILE MINIMIZING EXTERNAL INPUT OF N AND P IN POTATO CROPS

Location

Case-Study 6 (CS6) is positioned in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, more precisely in the province of East-Flanders in Belgium (GPS coordinates: 50°59'05" N, 3°47'13" E; Fig. 6.1). The climate is warm and temperate (mean annual temperature 10,5-11 °C, mean annual precipitation 800-900 mm). The soil texture of the field is sandy loam. Such soil types normally have no shortage of water or suffer from flooding's. Only during summer, problems with drought are possible.

Fig. 6.1. Location of Case Study 6.

Management practices implemented in the case study

Europe's agricultural landscape, with its growing emphasis on sustainability, is increasingly adopting advanced techniques such as green manure to enhance soil quality, reduce dependency on synthetic inputs, and promote environmentally friendly farming practices. Green manure, which involves planting specific crops like legumes (e.g. clover) and incorporating them into the soil before the main crop, offers significant potential for improving soil health. In Belgium, particularly in Flanders, sustainable practices are being embraced to address critical issues such as nitrate and phosphate leakage into water sources, deficits in soil organic matter, and a general decline in soil health, including degraded biological and structural conditions. However, the high population density in Flanders places additional pressure on biodiversity, further complicating these efforts.

In Flanders, the widespread high phosphorus (P) status of agricultural soils poses challenges, as excessive P can hinder microbial activity in the rhizosphere—a vital mechanism for nutrient cycling, especially in organic farming systems. Organic growers, who rely on rhizosphere activity for plant

nutrition, face the dilemma of balancing the use of organic manure to boost fertility with the risk of nitrate and phosphate leakage into surface and groundwater. To address this, effective soil management strategies are needed to prevent phosphorus surpluses by regulating external organic matter inputs.

Fig. 6.2. Experimental lay-out of Case Study 6. The experimental area is divided into 4 blocks (red frame) each containing one of six combined treatments (split-plot design): white colored-BAU (control) = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, no application of farmyard manure; white colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, no application of farmyard manure; green colored-BAU = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, and farm yard manure; green colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, and farm yard manure; yellow colored-BAU = conventional farming with cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated, and farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (grass clippings from nature reserves); yellow colored-AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, and farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material.

Case Study 6 focused on developing innovative soil management strategies for organic cropping systems. The objectives are twofold: to sustain soil quality and to achieve balanced phosphorus levels by investigating the combined effects of fertilization and differential cover crop management practices. The field experiment, conducted under an organic farming system, was established on a 0.216-hectare area divided into 24 plots (6 treatments × 4 replicates) using a split-plot design (Fig. 6.2). Non-inversion tillage practices were implemented, and no herbicides were used. Pest management relied exclusively on products permitted in organic farming. The nitrogen-to-phosphorus (N:P) and carbon-to-phosphorus (C:P) ratios of goat stable manure (farmyard manure, FYM) were adjusted by co-composting FYM with 'brown' material (grass clippings from nature reserves). The effects of co-composted FYM, compared to stockpiled FYM, on crop performance and soil quality were assessed over a multiyear field trial involving repeated applications of both fertilization products. The applied doses were calculated using the Flanders' phosphate fertilization standard as limiting factor. A control treatment with no base fertilization was also included. Within

the same trial, two distinct cover crop management strategies were applied: using cover crop mixtures as green manure or harvesting them as fodder crops. Variations in these treatments, in terms of both fertilization and cover crop management, are expected to result in differences in carbon (C), phosphorus (P), and nitrogen (N) inputs, potentially influencing main crop performance and soil quality.

The field experiments were carried out during the crop cycles of 2019 till 2023. In 2019, activities focused on setting up the experiment and standardizing field conditions for each treatment. During fall 2019, initial fertilization was applied according to the experimental layout, and the field was sown with a new cover crop mixture comprising 76% summer oats (*Avena sativa*), 12% pea (*Pisum sativum*), 3% Alexandrian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*), and 9% summer vetch (*Vicia sativa*). During subsequent cropping periods, a rotation of cover crops and main crops was maintained, with organic fertilizer application after incorporating the cover crop (Fig. 6.3): potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* var. *Vitabella*) in 2020, summer barley (*Hordeum vulgare* var. *Skyway*) in 2022, and savoy cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *sabauda* L.) in 2023. However, during the winter of 2021-2022, no cover crop was sown following the main crop because the winter leek crop was maintained throughout the winter season until the next main crop. Additionally, no samples or crop parameters were collected in 2021 with leek as main crop to ensure the sampling workload remained manageable and within the allowable limits for each case study.

Fig. 6.3. Overview of Case Study 6 with management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

Results revealed that crop yields in Case Study 6 were significantly and positively correlated with soil pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total organic carbon content (TOC), nitrate (NO₃) content, and exchangeable magnesium (Mg) and potassium (K) contents. These parameters are critical to soil fertility, nutrient cycling, and organic matter content, highlighting their importance in enhancing crop productivity. Conversely, crop yield showed a significant negative correlation with exchangeable iron (Fe) content. Excessive iron can cause plant toxicity, disrupt nutrient uptake, and induce stress that hinders growth. Furthermore, high iron levels may antagonize other nutrients, such as phosphorus, compounding their detrimental effects on crop performance. Yield analyses demonstrated that crops, including nitrogen-intensive ones like potatoes and savoy cabbage, yielded higher when the cover crop was incorporated into the soil rather than removed after mowing. Similarly, applying farmyard manure resulted in better yields compared to using compost but even more so compared to no fertilizer. A higher yield of the green cover crop mixture was also achieved when farmyard manure was applied. These findings suggest that the case-study was able to maintain, even improve, soil health conditions—through balanced pH, sufficient organic matter, optimal nutrient availability, and the avoidance of nutrient toxicities like iron overload—on its turn leading to improved crop yields.

Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria were the dominant microbial groups during the final year of the case study, with treatments showing no significant differentiation in microbial diversity. This highlights the stability of microbial communities despite variations in management practices. The dominance of Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria indicates a soil environment with strong nutrient cycling potential, favourable for plant growth and ecosystem functioning. These groups are often associated with high nutrient availability and efficient organic matter decomposition. Supporting this observation, no significant differences were detected in prokaryotic functional gene abundance related to carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles across treatments. However, a trend emerged, suggesting greater abundances when farmyard manure was applied compared to co-composted material, regardless of cover crop management. This pattern likely reflects the higher active nitrogen content of farmyard manure relative to compost and aligns with earlier observations of increased yields when cover crops were incorporated alongside farmyard manure application. Additionally, Actinobacteria contribute to soil health through the production of antibiotics that suppress pathogenic microorganisms. Meanwhile, the presence of Acidobacteria suggests soil resilience, as these microbes thrive in suboptimal conditions, still be able to break down complex organic materials but at a slower rate. This indicates the soil's capacity to maintain microbial activity even under environmental stress.

The Prokaryote diversity implies a balance between rapid nutrient cycling, effective organic matter decomposition, humus formation, resilience to stress and potential induced soil disease suppressiveness for all treatments applied. Functional gene abundance suggests a trend towards greater Prokaryote abundances when farmyard manure was applied regardless of cover crop management.

The treatment with farmyard (goat) manure containing “brown” co-composted straw combined with cover crops mowed and removed (AFVFYM) decreased overall fungal richness in the last monitoring year in CS6 experimental field compared to the control (cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, no fertilization). Decrease in overall fungal diversity due to goat manure was expected, since the fungal community may have changed more towards “manure specific” taxa. However, we could not link any of the measured soil derived factor into different treatments and changes in alpha diversity. We also detected a slight difference in fungal community composition between treatments and control and showed that fungal composition in treatments with farmyard manure containing “brown” co-composted straw and “pure” farmyard manure (FYM) were more similar with each other. Soil derived variables that were responsible for changes in total fungal community represented important soil health indicators linked to key ecosystem services related to nutrient and water balance (soil water content), total nitrogen content (Nt), electrical conductivity, K content and soil pH), and soil carbon (total organic C content). There was also a clear increasing trend in saprotrophic fungi in all treatments and a decreasing trend in pathotrophic fungi in AFVFYM and FYM. Furthermore, treatment changed the community composition of both saprotrophic and symbiotrophic fungi. Factors that seemed to be responsible of the variation in the saprotrophic fungal community in FYM and AFVFYM treatments included EC, FM, TOC, Nt and concentration of K. Manure has reported to increase electrical conductivity, TOC, Nt and to improve water stable soil aggregates parallel to our results.

In the last monitoring year, several fungi showed relationship to total organic soil carbon (TOC). For example, low TOC might promote the appearance of dark-septate endophytes that have potential to increase the tolerance of their host plants to abiotic stresses. Also, higher CEC and soil pH seem to increase certain saprotrophs and endophytes as well as common plant saprotrophs and pathogens which might contain potential to induce resistance against some plant pathogens. Although we could not detect a direct link between different fertilization treatment and specific fungi, different manure and co-composted straw and cover crop mowing and mixing treatments might have affected several fungi especially via changes in TOC.

For all treatments applied, including the control, a clear increase (almost always statistically significant) of the Shannon and Inverse Simpson index inferred from nematode communities was calculated. This is often a positive indicator of biological diversity, which is generally linked to improved ecosystem resilience and potential for nutrient cycling. However, the higher biological diversity most seemingly is due to a relatively larger portion of different species of herbivores like *Trichodorus*, *Tylenchorhynchus* and *Geocenamus* in the nematode community. This raises concerns. While biological diversity has increased, a higher proportion of herbivorous nematodes can indicate stress or disturbance in the soil environment, potentially harmful to plant health and crop productivity. The latter is supported by the fact that a decrease in the Structure Index is noted. This indicates towards a reduced functional diversity and thus less diversified soil food web which is critical for nutrient cycling, suppression of pests, and overall soil health. The increase in biological diversity contrasts with the decrease in functional diversity. This indicates that while there are more species present, the soil food web's organization and ability to perform ecosystem functions are impaired. A healthy soil ecosystem typically balances both biological and functional diversity. The

findings suggest that treatments of case-study 6 might be positively influencing yield as previously described but at the same time compromises the broader functional stability of the soil ecosystem. Soil management practices should aim to enhance both biological and functional diversity to support long-term soil health and sustainability. However, the conclusions drawn are not immediately applicable on case-study 6. Because the control shows the same trend as the treatments, the negative impact of the different farming management practices on the diversity of the soil nematode communities could not be demonstrated. More likely an external (climatological?) factor played an interfering role.

Notably there is a strong increase in earthworm number at the end of the experiment compared to the start in all management combinations. The delayed sampling time point due to the crop being maintained longer on the field than expected could be the reason. There is also no significant effect of the farming treatments on earthworm numbers. However, as expected, the addition of organic fertilizer increased earthworm numbers.

To summarize:

- **Incorporating cover crops and using farmyard manure effectively enhanced soil health and crop yields**, attributed to balanced soil pH, optimal nutrient availability, and reduced nutrient toxicities like iron overload.
- **Microbial diversity remained stable across treatments**, with dominant groups (Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria) supporting nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil resilience.
- **Farmyard manure treatments** influenced fungal community composition, **increasing beneficial saprotrophic fungi while decreasing pathotrophic fungi**, with key soil parameters like TOC and pH linked to these changes.
- While biological diversity increased, the decrease in functional diversity of nematode communities suggests potential soil ecosystem imbalances, possibly influenced by external factors rather than treatments alone.
- **All treatments showed a significant increase in earthworm numbers over time**, with organic fertilizer application further boosting populations, highlighting its role in promoting soil health.

Potential drawbacks

Fertilization that includes farmyard manure inevitably induce changes in fungal community and may decrease the overall richness. However, based on the obtained results we cannot speculate further about their potential drawbacks.

Although the quality of the potatoes (based on starch content) could be considered as normal for all treatments, the potato yield (2020) was generally low. The measured excessive nitrate nitrogen residues for potatoes in 2020 is in agreement with too limited crop development. Possibly the above

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ground problems with the Colorado bug and the powdery mildew had an influence. Alternatively, the nematode community revealed the presence of a larger portion of plant-parasitic nematodes potentially harmful for crop production. However more likely, the exceptionally dry year and no irrigation applied was the most important factor as potato tubers needs plenty of water to develop. It is known that climatological factors can overrule positive impacts of farming management practices.

CASE STUDY 7: COVER CROP MIXTURES: A PROMOTOR OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY IN POTATO CROPS?

Location

Case Study 7 (CS7) is positioned in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, more precisely in the province of West-Flanders in Belgium (GPS coordinates: 50°54'23.1" N, 3°07'41.9" E; Fig. 7.1). The climate is warm and temperate (mean annual temperature 10,5 °C, mean annual precipitation 836 mm). The soil texture of the field is sandy loam.

Fig. 7.1. Location of Case Study 7.

Management practices implemented in the case study

The western region of Belgium is a key area for potato and seed potato cultivation. Regional stakeholder meetings have highlighted that addressing soil-related issues is a top priority for improving potato production. The most pressing concerns identified include increasing soil organic matter (SOM), enhancing soil structure, and improving soil fertility. Among the management techniques discussed, the addition of organic matter or manure and the use of cover crops were ranked as the most effective solutions.

In organic agriculture, maintaining a rich and complex biodiversity within the soil is crucial. Soil biology must be capable of breaking down diverse organic materials to supply crops with adequate nutrients in a timely manner. Furthermore, soil microorganisms play a vital role in controlling soilborne diseases. Incorporating species-diverse cover crop mixtures can enhance soil biology, taking its functionality to a higher level.

The main objective of Case Study 7 was to test the impact of species-diverse cover crop mixtures in organic agriculture on soil biological diversity, as well as on the yield and quality of main crops. The study aimed to provide practical insights for farmers to optimize the design of their cover crop

mixtures. Additionally, the study sought to address key questions, such as whether species-diverse mixtures can combine multiple soil-beneficial functions, including nitrogen capture, and whether the inclusion of leguminous species in the mix contributes additional nitrogen to subsequent main crops. Advisors often recommend organic farmers to use species-diverse cover crop mixtures to stimulate soil diversity. However, little is known about the actual impact of these mixtures on soil diversity, either in the short or longer term.

The experimental design involved testing four different cover crop mixtures (Fig. 7.2). To enhance diversification, the number of species in each mixture was increased, with particular emphasis on the inclusion of leguminous species. Leguminous species add significant value as green manure through their symbiotic relationship with nitrogen-fixing bacteria, which capture nitrogen (N) from the atmosphere. The cover crops used were primarily frost-sensitive, typically dying off almost entirely by late winter. This characteristic facilitated easy mechanical destruction, enabling efficient soil preparation for the subsequent main crop.

Fig. 7.2. Diversity of the cover crop mixtures applied in case-study 7. 1 = Phacelia and Black oat, a "business as usual" mix; 2 = Phacelia and Egyptian clover, a simple leguminous/non leguminous mix; 3 = 5-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Winter vetch and Fodder radish, a medium diverse mix; 4 = 12-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Spring vetch, Fodder radish, Forage radish (Tillage radish), Pea, Lupin, Serradella, Niger, Alsike clover and Flax, a highly diverse mix.

It was decided to conduct the trial on one of the testing fields of Inagro's experimental farm for organic production (12 ha of fields). This farm is unique in Flanders and plays a pivotal role in advancing organic farming in the region. Its integration within the broader structure of Inagro facilitates a robust exchange of techniques and knowledge between organic and conventional farming methods. Since 2016, Controlled Traffic Farming (CTF) has been implemented on the Inagro organic farm. So, during the growing season, all field operations were carried out using a specially adapted tractor equipped with RTK-GPS technology (Fig. 7.3). This cultivation system preserves the 3-meter-wide planting beds from structural damage. Complementary to the introduction of CTF in 2016, ploughing was discontinued, instead soil and cover crops were managed according to reduced-till methods since. So in early spring, cover crop remains were flail mowed, and then only superficially worked in with a precision cultivator (till a depth of 3-5 cm). The preparation of the soil for sowing/planting the main crop consisted only of subsoiling (0-30 cm) and power harrowing (0-10 cm). After the main crop harvest, these same tools were again used to prepare the seedbed for the new cover crops. Fertilisation usually involved farmyard manure and/or commercial organic fertilizer pellets. Fertiliser type and application dose were determined based on soil analysis and an estimation of nitrogen mineralisation from soil organic matter (SOM) and crop residues.

Fig. 7.3. John Deere tractor with 3 m wide wheel axle.

Fig. 7.4. Overview of Case Study 7 with management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

Case Study 7 involved a multi-year trial designed to align with the fixed six-year crop rotation of the aforementioned farm (Fig. 7.4). This rotation includes both vegetable and arable crops ending with potatoes.

Main crops were:

- 2021 – broccoli - season 1
- 2022 - red beet - season 2
- 2023 - potato - season 3

Over three consecutive years (2020, 2021, and 2022), identical cover crop mixtures were sown post-harvest in the same locations and at consistent doses. The field experimental area was 0,162 ha divided according to a randomized block design into 16 plots (4 treatments x 4 replicates; Fig. 7.5).

Fig. 7.5. Experimental lay-out of case-study 7. The experimental area is divided into 18 plots of which 16 are occupied for the experiment: 1-4.01 = BAU ('business-as-usual') = Phacelia and Black oat; 1-4.02 = a simple leguminous/non leguminous mix = Phacelia and Egyptian clover cover crop; 1-4.03 = 5-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Winter vetch and Fodder radish = a medium diverse mix; 1-4.04 = 12-species mix including Phacelia, Black oat, Egyptian clover, Spring vetch, Fodder radish, Forage radish (Tillage radish), Pea, Lupin, Serradella, Niger, Alsike clover and Flax = a highly diverse mix.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The primary objective of Case Study 7 was to assess the impact of species-rich cover crop mixtures in organic farming on soil biodiversity, as well as the yield and quality of main crops. However, conclusions could not be drawn regarding the influence of chemical and physical soil parameters or microbial group abundance on crop yield and quality, as no significant correlations were identified.

Nonetheless, the study showed that the above-ground biomass production by cover crop mixtures is highly variable, with species ratios fluctuating significantly over the years. Factors such as sowing time, seed quality, soil condition, and weather conditions likely influenced these variations. The more

species-rich mixtures (5- and 12-species) consistently produced the highest and most stable total biomass yields.

Additionally, the study demonstrated a short-term increase in nitrogen availability to succeeding crops due to the cultivated cover crops. Nitrogen could be partially released from the biomass through mineralization following destruction (via frost and flail mowing) and subsequent incorporation into the soil. The amount of nitrogen released was directly related to the biomass of the cover crops, underscoring the importance of their effective development. This was most evident in the first two seasons, with more nitrogen present following the more complex mixtures (5- and 12-species), although significant differences were only measured in August 2021.

Finally, while more complex mixtures generally tended to positively affect the marketable yield and total above-ground biomass yield of the crops, these effects were not statistically significant. Caution is also warranted regarding plant pests and diseases. Complex mixtures may include plant species from the same family as the main crop, potentially serving as hosts for pests and increasing their impact on the subsequent main crop. For instance, in 2021, there was a small increase in rhizoctonia incidence, likely due to the presence of radishes (cabbage family).

The study also highlighted several important findings for soil health, emphasizing the limited impact of treatments on microbial diversity and overall abundance, while underscoring the role of soil properties in shaping microbial communities. Dominant microbial phyla included Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteriota, with no major treatment effects on their abundance. Diversity metrics such as alpha and beta diversity remained unaffected by treatments. However, specific gene abundances, particularly *nirK* and *ureC*, were influenced by cover crop mixtures, with *nirK* increasing in the 5-species mixture and *ureC* decreasing in the 12-species mixture. Balanced mixtures like the 5-species one may optimize conditions for specific microbial processes (e.g., denitrification), while more complex mixtures may create competitive or inhibitory effects that reduce the activity of some microbial groups. This underscores the need for thoughtful design of cover crop mixtures to maximize their benefits for soil microbial health and nutrient cycling. These genes, along with *cbbL*, were positively correlated with yield, suggesting their potential as soil health indicators. Soil physical and chemical properties, such as pH, electrical conductivity, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and moisture, significantly influenced microbial abundance. For instance, pH and electrical conductivity positively correlated with most microbial groups, while bulk density negatively impacted Gram-negative bacteria. Organic carbon fractions (TOC and POC) were linked to specific microbial and fungal groups, such as Gram-positive bacteria and Zygomycota fungi, while available phosphorus and micronutrients, particularly zinc, also promoted microbial abundance. Overall, the findings suggest that intrinsic soil properties, rather than management practices, play a crucial role in maintaining soil microbial health and productivity.

There are no indications that the different cover crops mixtures influenced fungal diversity or community composition during the final monitoring year, despite previous studies demonstrating a strong connection between cover crops and microbial communities. Only a decreasing trend in the relative abundance of symbiotrophs was observed in potato plots with different cover crops, particularly with the combination of Phacelia and Egyptian clover. This potentially results from a

combination of factors, including limited diversity in root exudates, potential competition, and the nitrogen dynamics of these simpler species. In contrast, complex mixtures provide usually a broader array of resources and conditions that support symbiotic fungal communities, fostering a more favorable environment for symbiotrophs despite the previous mentioned reduction of activity of some microbial groups due to competitive or inhibitory effects. However, this trend was not observed with the other cash crops and conclusion might be preliminary. Similarly, none of the measured soil-derived factors could be linked to the fungal communities from the treatments tested. Nonetheless, several factors, including CEC, Bs, Pav, and concentrations of Ca and Agsd_e, contributed to changes in the saprotrophic fungal community composition overall. To conclude, no evidence was found to suggest that the different cover crop mixtures applied, directly benefited soil fungi.

Nematode individuals increased significantly in the control treatment, while the effects of cover crop treatments varied, with less pronounced increases for 5- and 12-species mixtures and a decrease for the Phacelia/Egyptian clover mixture. A visual decline in relative proportions of the dominant nematode genera in the taxonomic profiles suggests a transition toward a more stable and mature community, accompanied by a notable increase in biodiversity across all treatments, including the control, between the start and the end of the experiment. This was evidenced by significant rises in Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices, as well as an increase in the Structure Index, pointing to greater taxonomic complexity. Various soil parameters shaped nematode community composition, but their influence was inconsistent, and external factors appeared to drive biodiversity changes more than specific treatments. Indicator genera trends revealed increases in some (e.g., *Coslenchus*, *Photorhabditis*) and decreases in others (e.g., *Acroboloides*, *Panagrolaimus*). Despite these community shifts, no relationship was found between nematode diversity and yield. Overall, while cover crops did not yet enhance biodiversity compared to the control, the findings underscore the role of external factors in promoting soil health and suggest the potential for longer-term benefits from cover crop use.

The earthworm densities were similar across treatments, with no significant differences observed. The highest abundance of endogenic species was found in the Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop treatment and the lowest in the 12-species cover crop mixture. Anecic species were most abundant in the 5-species cover crop mixture and least in the 12-species cover crop mixture, but differences were not statistically significant. No epigeic earthworms were found. These findings suggest limited treatment effects on earthworm populations and a need for further investigation into (longer-term?) experiments with complex cover crops potentially influencing soil fauna.

To summarize:

- No significant correlations were found between chemical and physical soil parameters or microbial group abundance and crop yield or quality. However, **nitrogen release from green cover crops through mineralization was observed**, benefiting subsequent crops, with the quantity of nitrogen tied to cover crop biomass.

- Cover crop mixtures did not significantly enhance microbial or fungal diversity compared to the control. While specific microbial genes showed treatment-related changes and correlations with yield, overall diversity metrics remained unaffected by treatments.
- Soil physical and chemical properties, such as pH, electrical conductivity, organic carbon fractions, and micronutrients like zinc, significantly influenced microbial abundance and community structure. These findings underscore the importance of inherent soil characteristics over management practices in shaping soil microbial health.
- **Nematode biodiversity increased across all treatments**, driven more by external factors than specific cover crop effects. Indicator genera trends suggested shifts toward a stable community. Earthworm densities also were unaffected by the different cover crop mixtures.
- **Species-rich cover crop mixtures tended to positively influence soil and crop health**, these effects were not statistically significant. Additionally, complex mixtures might harbor pest risks if they include species related to the main crop. Longer-term studies are needed to fully assess their benefits for soil fauna and health.

Potential drawbacks

Maintaining cover crop diversity throughout the growing period is challenging. In more complex mixtures, diversity often declines as certain plant species fail to thrive or grow unevenly due to varying climatic, environmental and soil conditions. Further research is essential to develop complex cover crop mixtures with balanced growth among species, ensuring that all plants in the mixture contribute effectively to the intended benefits.

CASE STUDY 8: INTENSIVE VERSUS EXTENSIVE VERSUS ORGANIC VEGETABLE FARMING

Location

Case Study 8 (CS8) is positioned in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, in the province of Antwerp, Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium and was managed by 'Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt' (PSKW, the Research Center for Vegetable Production) (Fig. 8.1). The climate is warm and temperate (mean annual temperature 11,5 °C, mean annual precipitation 716 mm). Due to the experimental design, case study 8 was carried out on two separate fields, one non-organic (GPS coordinates: 51°04'33" N, 4°31'46" E) and one organically certified field (GPS coordinates: 51°04'33" N, 4°32'19" E). Both fields were located within 1 km of each other. The soil texture of the field is sandy loam, with a superficial clay layer. Such soil types have relatively less chance of shortage of water, but the clay layer gives a higher risk of flooding.

Fig. 8.1. Location of Case Study 8.

Management practices implemented in the case study

In Belgium, approximately 45% of outdoor vegetable production occurs under intensive farming systems, while the remainder is cultivated within crop rotations that include arable crops, representing more extensive farming practices. Intensive vegetable production is characterized by limited crop rotation, intensive tillage, and unilateral fertilization. While this approach maximizes short-term productivity, it has significant drawbacks for soil quality and overall sustainability. It also fosters an environment conducive to pests and diseases, which can ultimately reduce crop yield and quality. By contrast, extensive farming practices—including broader crop rotations, reduced tillage, and increased organic matter input—are known to have a positive influence on soil biodiversity and resilience.

The aim of this case study is to explore ways to transition from intensive to more extensive farming practices. Specifically, the study will investigate how techniques such as non-inverting tillage, the application of organic matter, and increased use of cover crops can be feasibly implemented. These techniques are already recognized for their beneficial effects on soil health, yet their practical adoption requires careful consideration and collaboration with growers. Through this approach, the study seeks to provide actionable recommendations to farmers, demonstrating how these changes can improve soil life and biodiversity while addressing concerns about feasibility and potential impacts on yield. Organic vegetable farming systems are inherently more extensive due to their broad crop rotations, higher input of organic matter, and reduced reliance on synthetic crop protection agents. On average, these practices result in richer soil biodiversity. However, even within organic farming, there is variation between farms—some already implement extensive management practices, while others remain uncertain about their viability. This study aims to identify how organic farming techniques can further extensify their systems and determine whether similar effects on soil life can be achieved in conventional farming systems through the adoption of extensive practices.

Fig. 8.2. Crop management practices and main objectives in Case Study 8.

Case Study 8 provides a comprehensive comparison of farming approaches, contrasting conventional farming with organic farming, and intensive farming (characterized by conventional tillage and no cover crops) with extensive farming (which incorporates reduced tillage, cover crops, and compost applications) (Fig. 8.2). One of the primary objectives is to demonstrate to growers that investing in healthy soil—despite potentially slower immediate returns such as lower yields—can lead to long-term benefits in crop health and productivity. By building confidence in the tangible advantages of these practices, this study seeks to encourage broader adoption of sustainable farming techniques.

To facilitate the comparison of farming systems, two fields were used for this trial (2 x 0.1 ha). The first field had been conventionally cultivated for several years, following an intensive vegetable rotation. The second field, in contrast, had recently been converted to organic farming. During the two-year conversion period, the organic field was sown with a grass-clover mixture to improve soil quality and fertility. Both fields were further divided into two parts, each managed with a different cultivation system. This setup resulted in four distinct treatments, each of them consisting of four (semi-) replications of 120 m². (Fig. 8.3):

- **A – Organic and intensive:** organic fields are fertilized using organic fertilizer like cattle slurry, farmyard manure (cattle), and NK (11-3) organic fertilizer. Inverting tillage is utilized for soil management.
- **B – Organic and extensive:** similar to A, organic fertilizer is the primary source of soil nutrients in this treatment together with green waste compost. However, reduced tillage methods are implemented, and cover crops are used.
- **C – Conventional and intensive (control):** the intensively cultivated plots in this treatment are characterized by inverting tillage and the absence of cover crops in the crop rotation. Mineral fertilizers are used for soil nutrient supplementation.
- **D – Conventional and extensive:** in the conventional extensive treatment, compost is used along with chemical fertilizer for soil enrichment. Reduced tillage practices are employed in this approach and cover crops are used.

The trial was maintained during four growing seasons. The cropping cycle was as follows (*only in extensive treatments):

- Crop 1 (2020): Autumn Leek (var Oslo) *Allium porrum* Planting end of June, harvest end of October/November
 - *Cover crop 2021 *Phacelia tanacetifolia* + Crimson clover *Trifolium incarnatum*
- Crop 2 (2021): Celery (var Tango) *Apium graveolens* Planting end of June, harvest end of September
 - *Cover crop 2021 Ryegrass mixture
- Crop 3 (2022): Cauliflower (different varieties) *Brassica oleracea* var *botrytis* Planting in April and harvest in June Secondary crop Cauliflower Planting in July and harvest in October

*Cover crop 2022 *Phacelia tanacetifolia*

- Crop 4 (2023): Roman lettuce *Lactuca sativa* var *longifolia* Planting in June and harvest in July
Secondary crop Roman lettuce Planting in July and harvest in September

Fig. 8.3. Experimental lay-out of case-study 8. The experimental area is organised on 2 separate fields (A+B and C+D) each divided into 2 x 4 plots. A = organic intensive, B = organic extensive, C = conventional intensive, D = conventional extensive.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

By the end of the case study, the researchers visually observed that the soil quality of the extensive treatments (both conventional and organic) was superior compared to that of the intensive treatments, mainly demonstrated by faster water infiltration and a higher load-bearing capacity, which allows for quicker machinery access after rainfall. However, these properties were not reflected in the experimental data.

In terms of pest and disease management, conventional farming systems proved to be the more reliable choice, with the difference between intensive and extensive methods being less critical,

though extensive systems showed slight benefits for specific crops and diseases (e.g., celery leaf spot in the conventional system). Organic farming, however, may require additional strategies to handle higher pest and disease pressures.

Regarding yield and quality, extensive treatments consistently outperformed intensive ones across multiple crop types, regardless of whether the system was organic or conventional. Conventional farming systems delivered superior yields and quality for most crops compared to organic systems. Therefore, the choice of farming system depends on priorities: if sustainability or organic methods are preferred, extensive organic farming is the better choice; otherwise, conventional farming in either form can be opted for.

The crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total nitrogen (Nt) content, nitrate (NO₃) content, Pav content, and exchangeable Mg and K contents, cation exchange capacity (CEC) and the sum of bases (Bs). These parameters are critical to soil fertility, nutrient cycling, and organic matter content. Hence, the positive correlations suggest that a well-balanced, nutrient-rich soil is present supporting better crop performance and especially beneficial for crops which require more nitrogen like celery and cauliflower.

A higher abundance of microorganisms (excluding Actinobacteria) was positively correlated with increased crop yield. The dominant microbial phyla included Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteriota. The presence of these phyla indicates a soil environment rich in microbial activity, capable of maintaining nutrient cycling and contributing to a healthy soil ecosystem because these microbes play key roles in breaking down organic matter, cycling nutrients, and maintaining soil structure.

Beta diversity analysis revealed clear differences in prokaryotic communities between conventional and organic farming systems. These differences were influenced by factors such as soil pH, organic matter content, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and bioavailable metals. Gene abundance analysis further highlighted notable variations: conventional extensive farming exhibited higher levels of *amoA* (a gene crucial for nitrification) and *nirK* (associated with denitrification). This suggests that conventional extensive farming practices support microbial functions important for nutrient cycling, potentially enhancing short-term soil fertility. Indeed, elevated *amoA* levels could lead to increased nitrogen cycling capacity raising the risk of nitrate leaching, and immediate nitrogen loss through denitrification by elevated *nirK* activity, hence reducing soil nitrogen content over a short-time period. In contrast, organic intensive farming appears to maintain lower levels of these genes, possibly reflecting a more stable nitrogen reservoir and distinct microbial dynamics that favor long-term soil fertility with reduced nitrogen leakage. Furthermore, organic farming—particularly organic extensive practices—demonstrated higher overall microbial (bacteria and fungi) abundance and stronger correlations with soil health parameters, such as increased phosphorus content and organic matter. These factors collectively contribute to improved crop yields and better soil health.

The organic extensive treatment demonstrated significantly higher total fungal abundance, particularly of Zygomycota. Furthermore, extensive farming systems, regardless of whether they

were conventionally or organically managed, exhibited higher abundances of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), Ascomycota, and Basidiomycota.

Total nitrogen (Nt) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of AMF and Zygomycota, but no significant correlation was found with Ascomycota or Basidiomycota. These findings align with earlier studies, which suggest that symbiotic fungi, such as AMF, play a more direct and immediate role in plant nitrogen acquisition and nutrient cycling. In contrast, saprotrophic fungi are critical for the decomposition and mineralization of organic nitrogen but have a less direct impact on the immediate nutrient exchange processes required for plant uptake.

While fungal abundance varied across treatments, the farming systems did not appear to influence total soil fungal diversity significantly. However, specific fungal genera were identified as being indicative of one or more farming systems. Organic extensive farming was associated with different fungal genera compared to intensive conventional farming. Notably, a greater variety of saprotrophic fungi seemed to benefit from extensive conventional farming, confirming previous findings.

Changes in fungal community composition were driven by soil health indicators that influence ecosystem services related to nutrient cycling (e.g., cation exchange capacity and soil pH) and soil structure (e.g., the proportion of the smallest soil aggregate size class), which are essential for crop growth.

Nematode analysis revealed a higher Shannon index across all systems at the end of the experiment compared to the start, suggesting an increased biodiversity. Similarly, the Inverse Simpson index increased in all systems except the control. The rise in the Inverse Simpson index, most notable in the conventional extensive and organic intensive systems, indicates reduced dominance by one or a few species, leading to greater species evenness. In contrast, the control group likely experienced increased species richness or slight changes in evenness (sufficient to raise the Shannon index) while retaining dominance by a few species (which kept the Inverse Simpson index lower). The Structure Index also showed a slightly increasing trend in all systems except the conventional extensive farming system and the control. Although most results are not statistically significant, there is a noticeable trend towards a more balanced nematode community and thus potentially a more mature soil ecosystem in all farming systems compared to the control.

The nematode community compositions differed significantly between the farming systems at both the start and end of the experiments. This is likely due to the comparison of entire farming systems at two different locations with varying treatment combinations. Predominant genera in all systems included *Acrobelloides*, *Clarkus*, and *Pristionchus*. *Acrobelloides* is often linked to organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling, indicating an enrichment opportunist community. *Clarkus* is less frequently mentioned in soil studies, while *Pristionchus* is associated with decaying organic matter. Notably, *Pratylenchus* was prevalent at both the start and end of the experiment in all treatments. Species of the *Pratylenchus* genus are migratory endoparasites potentially having a broad host range, as a consequence, causing crop yield reductions and damage to various arable crops, including vegetables. The persistence of plant-parasitic nematodes across all systems suggests they benefit

from a general factor, most likely a suitable plant host (crop) and the absence of an effective soil suppressive disease capacity.

Many soil physical and chemical parameters significantly influenced nematode community compositions, albeit differently across farming systems. For example, organic matter (OM) and fine matter (FM) were key in shaping nematode communities in the conventional intensive treatment, while nitrogen (N_t), sodium (Na), and ammonium (NH_4) played significant roles in the conventional extensive treatment. These findings suggest that farming practices have a measurable impact on soil ecosystems. However, an overall conclusion concerning one of the farming systems, conventional versus organic or intensive versus extensive, remains difficult if not impossible.

The conventional extensive farming system clearly resulted in a higher earthworm density (statistically significant) compared to the other systems. When considering the organic systems solely, then also a higher earthworm abundance (not statistically significant) was noticed in the extensive approach. The increase was mostly caused by more endogenic and anecic species. No epigeic species were found. Earthworms play a critical role in improving soil structure, aeration, water infiltration, and nutrient cycling. Increased densities often correlate with healthier, less compacted soils and higher organic matter availability. The observation of higher earthworm densities in the conventional extensive farming system is a strong positive indicator of soil health. The absence of a notable increase in endogeic earthworms for intensive systems, suggests that these systems might not be as effective in fostering overall soil earthworm biodiversity and structure improvement as the extensive systems.

To summarize:

- **Extensive treatments (both conventional and organic) visually showed superior soil quality, with faster water infiltration and higher load-bearing capacity compared to intensive treatments.** This supports quicker machinery access after rainfall, although experimental data did not fully reflect these observations.
- The conventional systems (both intensive and extensive) seem to be more reliable for pest and disease management. The organic systems require additional pest and disease management strategies.
- Extensive systems outperformed intensive ones in yield and quality. Conventional farming systems delivered superior yields and quality for most crops compared to organic systems. If sustainability or organic methods are preferred, extensive organic farming is the better choice; otherwise, conventional farming in either form can be opted for.
- **Conventional extensive farming practices support microbial functions important for nutrient cycling,** potentially enhancing intensive short-term soil fertility. In contrast, organic intensive farming appears to maintain a more stable nitrogen reservoir and distinct microbial dynamics that favor long-term soil fertility with potentially reduced nitrogen leakage.

- While fungal abundance varied across treatments with the organic extensive system demonstrating a significantly higher total fungal abundance, the farming systems did not appear to influence total soil fungal diversity significantly.
- Although the nematode community compositions varied significantly by farming systems and were influenced by soil physical and chemical properties, a general trend towards a more balanced nematode community in all farming systems compared to the control was noticed. *Pratylenchus*, a plant-parasitic nematode, persisted across all treatments indicative of the absence of an effective soil suppressive disease capacity for any system.
- The conventional extensive farming system achieved the highest earthworm density, a positive indicator of soil health. Intensive systems were less effective in fostering overall earthworm biodiversity and soil improvement.

Potential drawbacks

Each of the cultivation methods requires its own way of working with its own set of tools. In order to be successful with any one treatment, the grower will need to build experience. Moreover, in order to get the financial reward from organic produce, the fields of the grower will have to be organically certified.

Some of the techniques applied in this trial did yield bad effects. E.g.: In the extensive treatments a cover crop was sown between two cultivations of cauliflower during summer, this reduced the available water for the following cauliflower crop because the cover crop evaporated more water compared to fallow land. Possibly, a combination of the techniques from the different treatments could improve results.

CASE STUDY 9: IMPROVING AGRO-ECOLOGICAL CROP PRODUCTION BY APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT SOURCES OF GREEN MANURE

Location

Case Study 9 is positioned in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region, more precisely in the region of Beveren, east-Flanders, Belgium (GPS coordinates: 51°16'03,5" N, 4°11'03,6" E; Fig. 9.1). The climate is warm and temperate (mean annual temperature 10,5-11 °C, mean annual precipitation 800-900 mm). The soil type of the field is classified as 'Pep' (texture class light sandy loam, drainage class wet and no soil profile development). Such soil types are normally wet and suffer from flooding's during winter time. They dry late during springtime but remain moisture during summer time.

Fig. 9.1. Location of Case Study 9.

Management practices implemented in the case study

Agricultural practices, particularly those associated with organic farming, are continually evolving due to advancements in research, technology, and local initiatives. In Belgium, the total area dedicated to organic farming remains limited, and the biodiversity value of the homogeneous agricultural landscapes in Flanders is notably low. This situation presents significant challenges in protecting biodiversity and ensuring the long-term survival of ecosystems and the essential services they provide.

Beyond further reducing the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, it is crucial to diversify production methods even more while actively involving farmers in landscape management. However, many farmers are reluctant to adopt biodiversity-supporting management practices, such as agro-ecological farming. This hesitation stems from the perception that these practices are unproductive, unprofitable, and heavily reliant on substantial subsidies, despite growing awareness

of their importance. However, some studies, such as van der Ploeg (2019), have demonstrated the potential of agro-ecological farming to be economically sustainable. Unfortunately, research of this kind is very limited and has yet to definitively prove that, over the long term, agro-ecological farming can foster economic resilience, reduce input costs, improve soil health, and enhance biodiversity. These characteristics make this way of farming a promising approach for sustainable agriculture. To gain broader acceptance from farmers and other stakeholders, further research is essential.

Case Study 9, organized by Pomona—a consumer-driven cooperative agroforestry farm—served as an example of sustainable agricultural management in practice. In this context, the field experiment followed an agro-ecological approach. The farming system included a no soil tillage or reduced tillage without conversion, combined with the application of green organic matter as fertilizer. Main crops were sown or planted manually, and no herbicides, pesticides, or other chemicals were used. A cover crop was cultivated between the main crops and incorporated into the soil after destruction.

Pomona's approach strives to achieve a perfect balance between a fully developed ecosystem and profitable crop production, while meeting consumer needs. In this regard, it was decided as primary objective of the case study to test various sources of locally produced organic fertilizers to increase soil organic matter (SOM) content, improve soil structure, and enhance plant health and development. In particular, farmyard manure compost and fermented organic waste (such as silage grass clover) were being evaluated. The experimental area covers approximately 1.2 hectares. Two rows, each measuring 8 meters by 300 meters (Fig. 9.2), are designated for the case study. Each row is subdivided into two plots, resulting in a total of four plots, one for each planned treatment. One plot did not receive any organic fertilizer, while the remaining three plots received different types of green manure: (i) farmyard manure, (ii) compost, and (iii) fermented organic material (grass silage). The first two types of green manure were produced locally, whereas the fermented grass was produced on the farm. In total, there are 16 plots (4 treatments x 4 replicates).

Fig. 9.2. Experimental area of Case Study 8.

The field experiments (Fig. 9.3) were conducted during the crop cycles from 2020 to 2023. The 2020–2021 cropping period was used solely to set up the experiment and homogenize the field conditions. Triticum spelta was grown across the entire field trial area (1.2 hectares), and no green manure or other fertilization methods were applied. During the 2021–2022 cropping period, Triticum spelta was again grown on the entire field trial area following the incorporation of a cover crop (Raphanus sativus). Before sowing the cover crop, fertilization was applied according to the aforementioned treatments. In the 2022–2023 cropping period, the field trial management mirrored the previous cropping cycle. However, instead of Raphanus sativus and Triticum spelta, Phacelia and Solanum tuberosum were cultivated. The latter consisted of a mixture of two varieties: S. tuberosum cv. Alouette and Cammeo (size 28–35 mm).

Fig. 9.3. Overview of Case Study 9 with management practices, crop cycle and data gathering.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

Case study 9 evaluated various locally produced organic fertilizers to increase soil organic matter (SOM) content, improve soil structure, and support plant health and development. For potato production, yields were higher when fertilization was based on silaged grass or compost, compared to both the control (no fertilizer) and farmyard manure. However, caution is advised when using farmyard manure, as it was linked to greater losses of marketable potatoes. In the case of *Triticum spelta* production, no significant differences in yield were observed among the treatments, and

farmyard manure did not negatively impact quality. These mixed results highlight the need for further research before recommending one or more of the practices as a reliable strategy.

Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria were the dominant prokaryotic phyla, with no major impacts of treatments on alpha diversity but a significant effect on beta diversity, linked to factors such as pH, yield, total nitrogen (Nt), available phosphorus (Pav), and soil aggregate stability (Agsd_c). Microbial abundances, including total microbial, bacterial (Gram-positive and Gram-negative), Actinobacteria, and Firmicutes, were not significantly affected by treatments. The same can be concluded concerning the gene abundances involved in the carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles. However, there was a general increase in gene abundance. Soil moisture emerged as a critical factor, showing a strong positive correlation with microbial abundance across all studied groups. Electrical conductivity (EC) positively correlated with the abundance of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria while bioavailable copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) had negative effects, with Cu reducing Firmicutes, and Zn reducing Gram-negative bacteria. Soil organic matter (SOM) and pH showed no significant impact on microbial abundance, while sodium exchange (Naex) positively influenced Gram-negative bacteria. These findings underscore the complex interactions between soil conditions, microbial communities, and environmental factors. Any correlation with the applied treatments is impossible. As mentioned before, recommending one or more of the practices as a reliable strategy is at this point unwise.

The overall richness and diversity of soil fungi, including Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi, Zygomycota, Ascomycota, and Basidiomycota, as well as community composition, were not significantly influenced. This finding was somewhat unexpected, given that manure-induced changes in soil fungal communities have been reported in previous studies.

As anticipated, certain saprotrophic fungi specialized in dung were positively associated with farmyard manure and composted green manure. Conversely, fungi with multiple ecological roles—such as pathogens, saprotrophs, and symbiotrophs—were positively associated with fermented green manure. These results align with earlier studies indicating that both mineral and organic fertilizers can drive differences in fungal communities. Notably, stronger differences might have been observed if the study had focused on the rhizosphere rather than bulk soil.

While no clear evidence of overall changes in fungal community composition was detected—likely due to high data variability—a set of soil-derived factors, including total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen (Nt), available phosphorus (Pav), and soil pH, appeared to influence fungal communities. These factors are associated with key processes such as carbon sequestration and nutrient cycling. However, no direct correlations with the applied treatments were identified, making it inadvisable to formulate specific recommendations based on these findings.

There was a decreasing trend in the relative abundances of all investigated fungal guilds when applying farmyard manure and fermented grass. This might indicate towards the appearance of more specialized fungal taxa which are probably not the most dominant ones. In addition, manure increases the soil pH which in turn slows the growth of fungi.

The experiment demonstrated that all treatments resulted in an increase in nematode abundance, accompanied by a more diverse nematode community by the end of the study. This increase suggests a positive impact on soil health, likely influenced by the application of cover crops, which appear to mitigate differences between fermentation treatments. While *Acrobeloides* remained the predominant genus, others such as *Aphelenchoides*, *Cruznama*, and *Pristionchus* were replaced by *Geocenamus*, *Rhabditophanes*, and *Pratylenchus*, the latter being a migratory endoparasitic genus capable of causing crop damage. *Acrobeloides*, often linked to organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling, indicate the soil continues to support enrichment opportunist communities. Their persistence suggests favorable conditions for organic matter breakdown and nutrient cycling. *Rhabditophanes*, bacterivores thriving in soils with high bacterial activity, are frequently associated with freshly incorporated organic matter or soil disturbances. Their emergence may reflect short-term microbial activity surges, potentially triggered by recent soil amendments or disruptions. Conversely, the increase in *Geocenamus* and *Pratylenchus* could signify stress within the soil ecosystem, potentially caused by nutrient imbalances or diminished microbial and nematode biodiversity, which might otherwise naturally suppress pests. Meanwhile, the decline of *Aphelenchoides*, *Cruznama*, and *Pristionchus*, genera typically associated with more balanced soil ecosystems, suggests a shift in soil conditions. This decline may indicate reduced biodiversity or changes in organic matter composition. The latter explanation is more plausible, as alpha diversity metrics (Shannon and Inverse Simpson indices) showed a non-significant increase across all treatments, reflecting greater community diversity. Additionally, the observed rise in the Structure Index, again indicating an improved (functional) diversity, was unrelated to specific organic fertilizer treatments. These results highlight the potential overriding influence of external factors—such as cover crop application—on nematode community dynamics, playing a more significant role in shaping these changes than the fertilization treatments themselves.

By the end of the experiment, the farmyard manure treatment exhibited the highest earthworm density, whereas the control treatment recorded the lowest. However, grass silage was the only treatment to demonstrate a clear increase in earthworm numbers from the start to the end of the experiment, although this increase was still not statistically significant. These findings suggest that grass silage may serve as a particularly suitable food source for earthworms, potentially supporting their development more effectively than farmyard manure or compost.

To summarize:

- **For potato production, silaged grass and compost yielded better results compared to farmyard manure and control treatments**, although farmyard manure was associated with greater losses of marketable potatoes. In *Triticum spelta* production, no significant yield differences were observed among treatments, and farmyard manure did not adversely affect quality.
- Microbial and gene abundances involved in the carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles abundances were not significantly affected by treatments. Complex interactions between soil conditions, microbial communities, and environmental factors could not be correlated to any of the applied treatments.

- The overall richness and diversity of soil fungi were not significantly affected though farmyard manure and compost influenced the abundance of dung-specialized saprotrophic fungi and a decreasing trend in fungal guilds was linked to treatments like farmyard manure and fermented grass, possibly reflecting shifts toward specialized taxa.
- **All treatments increased nematode abundance and diversity**, signaling improved soil health, with external factors like cover crops playing a more significant role than specific fermentation treatments. Shifts in nematode genera composition suggested changing soil conditions, including potential nutrient imbalances and biodiversity shifts.
- **Only grass silage showed a notable increase in earthworm numbers over time**, suggesting its suitability as a food source for earthworms compared to farmyard manure and compost.

Potential drawbacks

The potato crop suffered from blight disease (*Phytophthora infestans*). Since the disease was spread all over the field with no differences between the treatments, apparently the applied farming treatments could not reduce the problem by an improved soil condition and plant health.

The farmer experienced more difficulties to spread and mix the silaged grass on the field compared to the other fertilizers.

CASE STUDY 10a: BIOCONTROL OF SOIL-BORNE PHYTOPATHOGENIC FUNGI BY FUNGIVOROUS SOIL FAUNA COMMUNITIES IN CONVENTIONAL WHEAT CROPPING SYSTEMS

Location

Case Study 10a is part of the Continental pedoclimatic region and located in the German Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia near Nideggen with geographical coordinates of 50°42' N; 6°29' E (Fig. 10a.1). This location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 8.8°C and a mean annual precipitation rate of 600 mm.

Fig. 10a.1. Location of Case Study 10a.

Management practices implemented in the case study

Case Study 10a was established on a field of a commercial farm with a long-term conventional management, which included reduced (ploughless) tillage. The experimental design was a non-randomized block with one control and two treatments with $n = 4$ plots each (Fig. 10a.2). The experiment started in spring 2021 with a crop rotation (Fig. 10a.3) as follows: potato (2021), winter wheat (2022), winter barley (2023). The year 2022 was the experimental year.

The objective of Case Study 10a was to identify management practices that promote fungivorous soil fauna communities as antagonists of fungal plant pathogens (*Fusarium*) in conventional wheat production with reduced fungicide and fertilizer application rates. Furthermore, the efficacy of a biostimulant and a plant adjuvant in combination with an additive, was assessed for strengthening soil self-regulation processes and thus in controlling *Fusarium*. In this context, the following treatments (Fig. 10a.3) were established:

- 1) **Control:** Reduction of fungicides and fertilizers.

- 2) **Treatment 1:** Reduction of fungicides and fertilizers with use of an additive (Kantor) and a plant biostimulant (Nutri-Phite Magnum S).
- 3) **Treatment 2:** Reduction of fungicides and fertilizers with use of an additive (Kantor), a plant biostimulant (Nutri-Phite Magnum S) and a plant adjuvant (Smart-Seed G).

Control as well as Treatments 1 and 2 were supposed to reduce external input of plant protection measures and fertilizers with treatments 1 and 2 to support crop performance by innovative new products. Both treatments were new management practices introduced to the area.

Fig. 10a.2. Experimental design of Case Study 10a (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 10a.3. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in Case Study 10a.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The established treatments reacted with delay to the management adjustments. First effects were only found in the following year after establishment.

A plant biostimulant in combination with a plant adjuvant can promote collembolan diversity and thus contribute to a broader range of services they provide. The Biostimulant did not increase yields in the first two years, as it is often suggested.

Fungal richness and diversity did not differ between treatments. Biostimulants reduced abundances of pathogens (beneficial impact on plant health). Thus, plant stimulants with additives might have potentially compensated the decreased amount of fungicides and helped to decrease soilborne fungal pathogens (Muhorakeye et al. 2024). Several soil derived variables were detected that are explaining the variation of the total soil fungal community composition including those linked to the ecosystem services affecting nutrient cycling (CEC, EC, Bs, Nt, soil pH, and concentrations of Mg, Ca, K and B).

Nematode diversity significantly increased in all treatments from year 1 to year 3.

Potential drawbacks

Based on the fungal investigations in the CS10a field experiment about the effects of biostimulants combined with different plant adjuvants and additives, we cannot conclude any drawbacks related to their use. Since these kinds of supplements are often spread as foliar sprays, they might increase the cuticular permeability and furthermore alter the cuticular barrier to water loss (Räsch et al. 2018). But we did not find evidence on such.

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CASE STUDY 10b: BIOCONTROL OF SOIL-BORNE PHYTOPATHOGENIC FUNGI BY FUNGIVOROUS SOIL FAUNA COMMUNITIES IN ORGANIC POTATO CROPPING SYSTEMS

Location

Case Study 10b (CS10b) is part of the Continental pedoclimatic region and located in the German Federal State of Saxony-Anhalt near Trippigleben with geographical coordinates of 52°32' N; 11°9' E (Fig. 10b.1). This location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 9.2°C and a mean annual precipitation rate of 546 mm.

Fig. 10b.1. Location of Case Study 10b.

Management practices implemented in the case study

Case Study 10b was established on a field of a commercial farm with a long-term organic management and ploughing as tillage system. The experimental design was a non-randomized block with one control and two treatments with $n = 4$ plots each (Fig. 10b.2). The experiment started in spring 2021 with a crop rotation (Fig. 10b.3) as follows: potato (2021), winter wheat (2022), mustard (2023). The year 2021 was the experimental year.

The objective of Case Study 10b was to assess the biocontrol potential of fungivorous soil fauna communities in terms of phytopathogenic fungi (*Fusarium* and *Alternaria*) and their mycotoxins as well as to promote fungivorous soil fauna communities in organic potato cropping systems. In this context, the following treatments (Fig. 10b.3) were established:

- 1) **Control:** no undersowing according to local practice.
- 2) **Treatment 1:** strip undersowing in furrows.

3) **Treatment 2:** broad undersowing in furrows and on ridges.

Treatments 1 and 2 were supposed to strengthen soil intrinsic self-regulating processes by diversification (two different seeding regimes) with undersown crops: *Vicia sativa*, *Linum usitatissimum*, *Lolium perenne*, *Trifolium resupinatum*, *Guizotia abyssinica* (13.5 kg ha⁻¹). Both treatments were new management practices introduced to the area.

Fig. 10b.2. Experimental design of Case Study 10b (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 10b.3. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in Case Study 10b.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

Undersown crops in organic potato cultivation promote the abundance of microarthropods and the diversity of collembolan communities and thus the ecosystem services they provide. Generally, undersown crops have a positive effect on yield quality (grain moisture) and yield quantity in the following year. Broad undersowing is more beneficial to soil fauna and crops than strip undersowing.

Two phytopathogenic fungi species were detected: *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Alternaria alternata*. Fungal DNA amounts did not significantly differ between treatments. Mycotoxin concentrations were below the limits of detection in all samples. No conclusions can be drawn regarding the promotion of mycotoxin bioregulation.

Both treatments, especially broad undersowing, increased fungal diversity and might have the potential to reduce plant diseases. *Trichoderma atroviride* showed positive response to both treatments and this fungus is a promising biocontrolling agent to promote antagonism and induction of plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005). Furthermore, common saprotrophic fungi with ability to decompose xylan and cellulose (Domsch and Gams 1969) and dung might be favoured by broad undersowing. Whereas strip undersowing might for example favour fungi with cellulolytic properties and ability to decompose wood (Okada et al. 1993, Giraldo & Grous 2019). Broad undersowing might have the potential to increase saprotrophs.

Both treatments showed an increase in nematode diversity from year 1 to year 3. However, the impact of year is stronger than the impact of treatment.

Potential drawbacks

Positive effects on microarthropods only occur in the year of cultivation of undersown crops; no legacy effects on soil fauna were detected. Based on the fungal and nematode investigations, we cannot conclude any drawbacks related to their use.

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CASE STUDY 11: POTENTIAL OF PLANT DIVERSITY TO PROMOTE INTRINSIC SOIL SELF-REGULATION PROCESSES AND TO ENHANCE FUNGIVOROUS SOIL FAUNA COMMUNITIES IN WHEAT CROPPING SYSTEMS

Location

Case Study 11 (CS11) is part of the Continental pedoclimatic region and located in the German Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia near Nideggen with geographical coordinates of 50°42' N; 6°29' E (Fig. 11.1). This location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 8.8°C and a mean annual precipitation rate of 600 mm.

Fig. 11.1. Location of Case Study 11.

Management practices implemented in the case study

Case Study 11 was established on a field of a commercial farm with a long-term conventional management, which included reduced (ploughless) tillage. The experimental design was a non-randomized block with one control and two treatments with $n = 4$ plots each (Fig. 11.2). The experiment started in autumn 2020 after rape seed with a crop rotation (Fig. 11.3) as follows: winter wheat (2021), maize (2022), winter wheat (2023). The year 2021 was the experimental year.

The objective of Case Study 11 was to assess the potential of plant diversity in conventional wheat cultivation to reduce fungal diseases through phytopathogenic *Fusarium* species by promoting antagonistic fungivorous soil fauna, and to enhance soil self-regulatory processes. In this context, the following treatments (Fig. 11.3) were established:

- 1) **Control:** Single seed rows (12.5 cm wide) with plant protection according to local practice.

- 2) **Treatment 1:** Extensive farming with wide seed rows (20 cm) and no plant protection.
- 3) **Treatment 2:** Diversified extensive farming with wide seed rows (20 cm), no plant protection and clover undersowing.

Treatments 1 and 2 were supposed to increase associated plant diversity within the crop, with treatment 2 also enhancing sown plant diversity. Both treatments were new management practices introduced to the area.

Fig. 11.2. Experimental design of Case Study 11 (left) and images of the experimental treatments (right).

Fig. 11.3. Management practices implemented and depiction of the objectives pursued in Case Study 11.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The established treatments reacted with delay to the management adjustments. First effects were only found in the following year after establishment.

Clover undersowing in wheat cultivation promotes soil fauna like microarthropods (collembolans and mites) without a negative effect on yield quantity and quality. The composition of the clover undersowing is important: Potential host plants for phytopathogenic *Fusarium* species should be avoided as for instance red and white clover.

At fungal OTU level, various soil fungal representatives showed positive indications to treatments. Fungi that showed positive associations with extensive farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides included fungi with various ecological roles for example as potential biocontrolling agents against fungal plant pathogens (Lombard et al. 2015, Khairullina et al. 2023). On the other hand, fungi that showed positive associations with diversified extensive farming with wide seed rows and undersown clover without pesticides included for example common plant pathogenic fungal genus *Fusarium*, which however contain also species acting as root-endophytes and biocontrollers of some plant pathogens (de Lamo et al. 2020).

Potential drawbacks

The experiment showed that a promotion of antagonistic fungivorous soil fauna for bioregulation of *Fusarium* and its mycotoxins could not be demonstrated. Results indicated that both diversification treatments without pesticides can also lead into decreasing of putative beneficial saprotrophic fungi, and species of *Trichoderma*, which can act as biocontrollers of fungal and nematode plant pathogens and induce plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005 Yao et al. 2023).

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CASE STUDY 12a: IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT AND TILLAGE PRACTICES ON SOIL BIOTA

Location

Case Study 12 (CS12) in the Nemoral region explored the impact of tillage practices on the pesticide residues and soil fauna in no-till, reduced tillage, and conventional tillage in cereal fields and in organic and conventional farming.

More specifically, the study was divided into two sub-activities (specified as CS12 and CS12a):

- **CS12** — management practices and soil biodiversity in reduced tillage and no-tillage cereal fields with data collection in 2019 and 2020
- **CS12a** — study of the impact of no-tillage and conventional tillage systems on soil biology and soil quality in organic and conventional farming with data collection from 2021 to 2023.

The Case Study 12 was conducted in five different locations across Estonia, and data was collected from 10 fields (three replications from each field) located in the counties of Viljandi, Põlva, Lääne-Viru, Saare and Pärnu (Fig. 12a.1). In the Põlva and Lääne-Viru regions, the fields represented no-tillage practices, and in the other three regions, the data was collected from reduced tillage fields. The annual temperature and mean annual precipitation for the locations were 7,7°C and 905 mm (Viljandi region), 8,5°C and 539,8 mm (Põlva), 6,9°C and 747,4 mm (Lääne-Viru), 9,2°C and 637,6 mm (Saare) and 8,8°C and 784,4 mm (Pärnu).

Fig. 12a.1. Case Study 12 locations for data collection in five regions in Estonia (reduced tillage and no-tillage fields)

The Case Study 12a was located in southern Estonia in Nõo municipality (Fig. 12a.2). The location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 7.2°C, mean annual precipitation of 557.73 mm, and an annual potential evapotranspiration of 568.68 mm.

Fig. 12a.2. Soil conditions for Case Study 12aA (left), the plots (upper right), and location in Estonia (lower right). In main proportion the typical soil on field is Stagnic Luvisol (LP) accompanied by Gleyic Luvisol (Klg)

Management practices implemented in the case study

During the Case Study 12a, we implemented three main management practices, those were conventional farming under no-tillage, conventional farming under tillage and organic farming under conventional tillage (Fig. 12a.3). For soil biodiversity assessment was included green edge next to the no-tillage field system. It is stated that the over-usage of pesticides will harm the agricultural soils whilst the accumulation and influence of pesticides might be especially harmful on no-tillage farming systems. On other hand, no-tillage farming system will preserve the soil quality and properties that are needed for food production (Dhuldhaj et al 2023; Sarker et al 2024; Sun et al 2018).

Fig. 12a.3. Concept for Case Study 12*

* The field data collection for CS12 and CS12A did not include potatoes. Potato farmers were surveyed with a separate questionnaire survey in 2020.

Biodiversity status

In Case Study 12A of the Nemoral region, while the small sample size limited the inference of treatment effects on prokaryotic diversity, soil pH was found to be significantly associated with the prokaryotic community compositions. Interestingly, no associations were identified between the top 40 most abundant prokaryotic genera and the measured environmental parameters. Regarding functional gene abundance in the same case study, bioavailable manganese (Mnba) showed a significant association with the variation of overall functional groups. Furthermore, actual field moisture content (Fma) and ammonium (NH₄) exhibited strong positive correlations with all examined genes.

Concerning fungal diversity in CS12A, only a few soil-derived variables significantly explained the variation in the total fungal community composition in 2022, with Pav (likely referring to a soil physical parameter not fully defined in the excerpts) and the second largest soil aggregate distribution class pointing towards the non-cultivated field edge. The variation in saprotrophic fungal community composition in CS12A was explained by manganese concentration along the first principal component (PC1) and other variables along the second principal component (PC2), including cation exchange capacity (CEC), organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), base saturation (Bs), and concentrations of magnesium (Mg) and calcium (Ca). A divergence in the community composition of pathotrophic fungi between treatments was observed in the last monitoring year in CS12A. Soil pH, pointing away from the treatment towards the non-cultivated field edge, and the concentration of sodium (Na) were the significant variables explaining the variation of the pathotrophic community composition.

For nematode diversity in CS12A, only three out of 31 physical and chemical parameters – magnesium (Mg), ammonium (NH₄), and molybdenum (Mo) – significantly shaped the nematode communities. An NMDS plot suggested that ammonium (NH₄) potentially influenced the nematode community composition in 2023.

Regarding the relationship between soil properties and microbial abundance in CS12A, the soil organic fraction was generally the determining factor for microorganism abundance. Specifically, the contents of organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), and total nitrogen (Nt) were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram-positive bacteria). Moreover, particulate organic carbon (POC) content showed a positive and significant correlation with the abundance of Gram-positive bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria) and with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi. Additionally, the available manganese (Mnav) content was significantly and positively correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi.

In terms of the relationship between soil properties and crop yield in CS12A, crop yield was found to be significantly and positively correlated with exchangeable sodium (Na_{ex}) content. Conversely, it was significantly and negatively correlated with calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content and with electrical conductivity (EC).

The first factor in the earthworm analysis for CS12A explained only 10% of the variation. On this factor, the predictors Nt (total nitrogen), POC (particulate organic carbon), CEC (cation exchange capacity), and FMa (actual field moisture content) loaded positively, while BD (bulk density), Pav (likely a soil physical parameter), and NO₃ (nitrate) loaded negatively. On the second factor, Agsd_e (likely related to soil aggregate size distribution), and NH₄ (ammonium) loaded positively, and Agsd_b, Agsd_c (likely related to other soil aggregate size distributions), and pH loaded negatively.

The earthworm abundance was significantly lower under conventional tillage compared to no-till and organic farming in CS12A. This is attributed to the negative impact of frequent soil disturbance in conventional tillage on earthworm populations, leading to reduced abundance and biomass. Organic farming, conversely, resulted in the highest earthworm abundance and biomass, likely due to the absence of synthetic chemicals and the use of organic amendments. Field edges also exhibited higher

earthworm abundance compared to conventionally tilled fields, similar to no-till and organic fields, benefiting from less disturbance and a more diverse habitat. The comparison of no-tillage and reduced tillage in CS12 fields, indicated higher earthworm biomass for no-tillage fields, while the earthworm abundance results varied across the regions and practices.

Conventional tillage can lead to soil structure degradation, increased erosion, and loss of organic matter, negatively impacting soil health. No-tillage farming may face challenges with weed management and can potentially lead to soil compaction in certain soil types. Organic farming, while beneficial for earthworms, may require more labor and potentially result in lower yields compared to other systems. Field edges, while promoting biodiversity, could potentially harbor pests and diseases.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

Fungi:

In the Case Study 12A field experiment (Nemoral region), no direct relationship was found between treatments/soil factors and dominant fungal taxa. However, organic farming with conventional tillage showed a trend toward increased fungal diversity compared to the control. Trends also suggested differences in fungal community composition between the control and other treatments. Saprotrophic fungal community variability was linked to manganese concentration, CEC, organic matter, TOC, base saturation, and magnesium/calcium concentrations. Pathotrophic fungal community variability was linked to soil pH and sodium concentration. In 2022, organic farming with conventional tillage showed an increasing trend in Shannon diversity. Pathotroph abundance decreased in conventional no-tillage farming but increased in organic farming with conventional tillage in the last monitoring year. Symbiotroph abundance also showed an increasing trend in organic farming with tillage in the last two monitoring years.

Nematodes:

Based on the research results, ammonium and magnesium are consistently identified as key drivers shaping nematode communities, with ammonium often having a strong, sometimes negative, impact on nematode diversity and structure at study fields.

Earthworms:

Under conventional tillage management, earthworm abundance was significantly lower compared to no-till and organic farming practices. Therefore, it is recommended to minimize soil disturbance and use no-tillage methods. Organic farming practices resulted in the highest earthworm abundance, indicating that the absence of synthetic chemicals and the use of organic amendments support earthworm populations. Thus, it is recommended to add organic amendments or incorporation of stubble into the soil. Field edges had higher earthworm abundance compared to conventionally tilled fields, so it is advisable to preserve field edges. These practices help maintain healthy and abundant earthworm communities. This, in turn, supports soil health and nutrient cycling, contributing to sustainable agricultural systems.

Microbes:

Recommended Strategies: The soil organic fraction generally determined the abundance of microorganisms. The contents of organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC), and total nitrogen (Nt) were positively correlated with Firmicutes bacteria, while the content of particulate organic carbon (POC) was positively correlated with Gram-positive bacteria and Zygomycota fungi. Therefore, it is recommended to increase soil organic matter content using organic fertilizers. The content of available manganese (Mnav) was positively correlated with Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Sufficient organic matter content creates a favorable environment for various microorganisms. This contributes to improved nutrient cycling and soil fertility.

Potential drawbacks

Different Soil Management Practices

Conventional tillage: Frequent soil disturbance in conventional tillage can lead to soil structure degradation, increased erosion, and loss of organic matter. This negatively impacts soil health and its ability to support crop growth. The intensive nature of conventional tillage significantly reduces earthworm abundance and biomass. Earthworms are crucial for nutrient cycling and soil aeration, and their decline can impair soil fertility and ecosystem functioning.

No-tillage: Transitioning to no-till farming requires substantial initial investment in specialized machinery and equipment. This financial barrier can be a significant drawback for small-scale farmers or those with limited resources. In no-till systems farmer faced challenges with weed management, as the absence of soil disturbance can lead to increased weed pressure. This may necessitate the use of herbicides, which can have environmental and economic implications.

In some parts of the field parcel we observed that, no-till practices can lead to soil compaction, particularly in heavy or poorly drained soils. This can affect root growth and water infiltration, potentially reducing crop yields also earthworms community.

Organic farming: Organic farming practices often require more labour for activities such as manual weeding, as we also observe on field but in other hand it supported the earthworm activity on the field. The yields remained lower if to compare to other soil management systems. This yield gap can impact the economic viability of organic farming for some producers.

Field edge(s): while beneficial for biodiversity, can also harbour pests and diseases that may spread to adjacent crops. Managing these edge effects requires careful monitoring and integrated pest management strategies that can be part of future project development. Allocating land for field edges and buffer zones can reduce the overall area available for crop production. This trade-off between biodiversity conservation and land use efficiency must be carefully balanced.

Soil Biota, Microbes, and Nematodes: While promoting soil biodiversity is generally beneficial, shifts in microbial communities and nematode populations can sometimes lead to unforeseen consequences. For example, the proliferation of certain pathotrophic fungi or imbalances in nematode communities could potentially increase the risk of plant diseases or negatively impact

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nutrient cycling processes. Similarly, while increasing soil organic matter primarily supports beneficial microbes, it also creates opportunities for diverse microbial activity, which can enhance nutrient cycling and dynamic soil processes, helping to sustain a healthy and balanced soil ecosystem over time. Ammonium and magnesium are consistently identified as key drivers shaping nematode communities, with ammonium often having a strong, sometimes negative, impact on nematode diversity and structure at study fields.

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CASE STUDY 12b: DIRECT IDENTIFICATION OF AIRBORNE INOCULUM REVEALS EFFECTS OF AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT ON PHYTOPATHOGENIC FUNGI

Location

Case Study 12b (CS12b) is located in Rannu, Tartu County, Estonia (58.301194, 26.307278; Fig. 12b.1, Fig. 12b.2). The location is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 7.2°C, mean annual precipitation of 557.73 mm, and an annual potential evapotranspiration of 568.68 mm.

Fig. 12b.1. Case Study 12b spore sampler position in wheat field and field location in Estonia.

Management practices implemented in the case study

The CS12B, conducted as part of the SoildiverAgro project, aimed to improve current disease management strategies in wheat and potato fields by utilizing airborne inoculum spore traps. The overarching goal was to reduce the routine application of fungicides and instead implement a more targeted approach based on the actual presence of disease-causing spores in the air and prevailing weather conditions. This aligns with the European Green Deal's objective to significantly decrease the use of chemical pesticides. The study focused on a conventional winter wheat field in Tartu County, Estonia, at Rannu Seeme LLC during the 2021 growing season (April to November), with continued sampling planned for subsequent years.

Installation of a Spore Trap and Weather Station: A Burkhard 7-day recording volumetric spore trap was installed in the middle of the winter wheat field (Fig. 12b.1, Fig. 12b.3). This type of spore trap continuously collects airborne particles, including fungal spores, over a seven-day cycle. Alongside the spore trap, an **on-site weather station** was set up to record crucial climatic conditions, such as soil moisture, temperature, and precipitation. The combined data from the spore trap and the weather station was intended to create a reliable tool for predicting potential grain disease risks.

Fig. 12b.2. Soil conditions for Case Study 12b (left). In main proportion the typical soil on field is Stagnic Luvisol (LP) accompanied by Gleyic Luvisol (LP(g)).

Fig. 12b.3. Implementation of a decision support system at Case Study 12b.

To facilitate targeted Integrated Pest Management (IPM), several key management practices were implemented.

Differential Fungicide Treatments: The experimental field was divided into two distinct treatment areas.

Untreated Control Area a 100 m² area directly surrounding the spore trap was deliberately left **untreated** with fungicides. This served as a baseline to observe natural disease development in the absence of chemical intervention.

Conventionally Treated Area the remaining portion of the field was managed following **conventional practices**, which included the application of recommended fungicide treatments.

Monitoring of Airborne Inoculum. The Burkhard spore trap continuously collected airborne fungal spores. Each week, the collection tape from the spore trap was replaced, and the captured biological material was subjected to laboratory analysis. **DNA extraction and quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)** techniques were employed to identify and quantify the concentrations of specific fungal pathogens, including *Zymoseptoria tritici* (causing wheat leaf blotch), *Blumeria graminis* (causing powdery mildew), and *Fusarium spp.* (causing Fusarium head blight). This allowed for the monitoring of the presence and abundance of disease-causing organisms in the air over time.

Visual Disease Assessments. Throughout the growing season, **visual assessments of cereal diseases were conducted in both the untreated and conventionally treated areas.** These assessments provided a direct measure of disease severity and progression on the plants. For the most significant diseases observed, **Area Under the Disease Progress Curve (AUDPC) values were calculated** to quantify the overall disease impact over the season.

Analysis of Soil Parameters and Biodiversity. In addition to monitoring airborne pathogens and plant diseases, the study also investigated the impact of these management practices on the soil ecosystem. **Soil physical and chemical parameters were analysed** in both treatment areas. Furthermore, the **diversity of earthworms and the soil microbial biomass were calculated** to assess the broader ecological effects of the disease management strategies.

The data collected through these management practices, particularly the spore counts and weather data, was intended to identify the main infection risk periods for key fungal diseases. The goal was to enable disease detection even before visible symptoms appeared on the plants, allowing for **more precisely timed fungicide applications**, thus avoiding unnecessary treatments and promoting ecological sustainability. Preliminary results from the 2021 growing season indicated that traditional fungicide application timings might not always coincide with the periods of highest spore load and favourable environmental conditions for infection, suggesting the potential for optimization based on spore monitoring. The continuation of this case study in subsequent growing seasons aimed to further validate these findings and contribute to the development of DNA-based prediction systems for foliar disease outbreaks.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

Case Study 12b does not provide explicit recommendations regarding strategies for enhancing soil biological diversity within the context of this research, nor do they elaborate on the principal benefits

of such diversity. The primary focus of the study was on the transmission of airborne fungal diseases and the prevalence of septoria leaf blotch (*Zymoseptoria tritici*) in winter wheat.

Although the research included analyses of soil physical and chemical parameters, as well as assessments of earthworm diversity and soil microbial biomass, the sources did not outline specific strategies for improving these indicators, nor did they offer a detailed discussion on the direct benefits of soil biological diversity in relation to the studied plant diseases. Soil fungal analyses were not conducted for Case Study 12b.

The SolidverAgro project revealed that the amount of *Z. tritici* spores, which cause wheat leaf blotch, varies significantly during the growing season. This is due to the long latency period of the plant disease with symptoms which can appear weeks after infection. Therefore, it is especially important to time spraying correctly. Most treatments against leaf blotch are carried out around May 20. In the 2021 control spraying was actually needed in the first week of June, when there was enough moisture for infection and the amount of pathogen spores in the air had also increased strongly.

Second spraying is generally done in the third week of June. The 2021 monitoring data showed that spraying was only needed at the end of June. Based on these results, it can be concluded that to precisely time fungicide treatment an accurate assessment of the fungal spores in the air is essential (Kay et al 2024; Kerdraon et al 2024).

Potential drawbacks

While the use of spore sampler technology offers significant promise for improving disease management in agriculture, several potential drawbacks and challenges were identified during the case study.

One key challenge relates to the **technology's operational dependence on weather conditions**. Specifically, the study noted that the **performance of the solar panel and battery, which power the spore sampler, can be influenced by weather**. The case study highlighted that **installing a sufficient battery is crucial to ensure the continuous operation of the spore sampler**. Furthermore, a practical difficulty encountered was the **lack of support from the spore sampler vendor regarding the selection and installation of a suitable solar panel and battery system**. This lack of assistance could present an obstacle for farmers adopting this technology.

Beyond technical aspects, the **logistical requirement of regular sample collection** poses another potential drawback. The study mandated that **spores must be collected every week on the same day and time**. This necessitates a consistent commitment from farm personnel and could add to their workload. The **inherent risks associated with using technology** should always be acknowledged. This could encompass equipment malfunctions, data loss, or other unforeseen technical issues, emphasizing the need for **considering and mitigating these risks**.

Finally, while spore samplers can detect the presence of airborne pathogens before visual symptoms appear, the **interpretation of the collected data and the subsequent development of effective disease management strategies necessitate region-specific knowledge and prediction models**. The case study explicitly mentioned the **need for developing DNA-based prediction systems tailored to**

the specific conditions of the region. It was noted that existing systems from other parts of the world are not directly transferable and applicable.

In summary, while spore samplers offer valuable insights for proactive disease management, their effective implementation requires addressing challenges related to power reliability in varying weather, the commitment to regular sampling, general technological risks, and the necessity of developing region-specific data interpretation tools and prediction systems.

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CASE STUDY 13: INCREASE OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY THROUGH AMENDMENT OF FOREST BASED ORGANIC MATERIAL IN POTATO CROPS

Location

The Case Study 13 (CS13) field experiment in the Boreal region was established in Laitila, south-western Finland (Fig. 13.1), in early potato field under conventional farming.

Fig. 13.1. Location of Case Study 13.

Management practices implemented in the case study

The experiment layout was a randomized complete block design with four replicates with a total of 12 plots, each measuring 16 by 23 m (Fig. 13.2). The amendments were spread into the experimental plots once in the end of June 2020 and rates used for the sludges at their original moisture content were 50 t ha⁻¹. The two soil amendments, composted pulp mill sludge (CPMS) and fiber sludge (FS), used in the experiment were produced by Soilfood Oy from organic side streams provided by Stora Enso's Imatra Mill located in southeastern Finland. CPMS and FS consists of cellulose fibres that are too short for the final product of the mill. The main difference between the materials is that CPMS recovered from the mill's wastewater treatment process contain phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), and other nutrients added to the biological purification step to cut down oxygen demand of effluent waters, whereas FS is a nutrient-poor cellulose material from the pre clarifier of cardboard machine process water, removed in a wire sieve as semi-dry mass. Sampling for soil and biological diversity analyses were conducted in autumn. Before planting, field was ploughed, harrowed, and milled. Seed potatoes (early variety Timo) were planted (3000 kg ha⁻¹) each year in the CS13 field on mid-April and crop was harvested on mid-June. Experimental field plots had received mineral NPK fertilization (N, 44kg; P₂O₅, 18.4kg; K₂O 70.4kg), and diammonium phosphate (N 8.4kg; P₂O₅ 9.6kg) and herbicides (Proman, metobromuron 0.152kg; Fenix, aclonifen 0.168kg; Senkor, metribuzin, 0.027 kg) right after planting.

Fig. 13.2. Experimental lay-out of Case Study 13. The experimental area is organized in four blocks each divided into three plots. CTRL = control, FS= fiber sludge, CPMS = composted pulp mill sludge.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The cultivation period of early potato in Finland is short, 1.5-2 months, so the soil for most of the year is bare making it prone to erosion and nutrient loss. Earlier results have shown promising positive effects of organic amendments processed from the side-streams of forestry and pulp industry on soil structure and microbiology on arable soil (Rasa et al. 2021, Peltoniemi et al. 2023).

- There was no effect of organic forest-industry derived organic soil amendments on prokaryotic, fungal or earthworm diversity and composition. Functional 16S rRNA gene abundances were not affected by organic soil amendments either.
- There was a strong negative correlation with CEC and stem rot causing fungal potato pathogen *Neocosmospora rubicola*. The result is interesting, since CEC is suggested to be one of the most important indicators of soil fertility (Xu et al. 2022). Low CEC in conventionally farmed early potato field might expose soil to fungal pathogens due to decreased ability of soil to retain and supply nutrients.
- Although some changes in the number and diversity of nematode community were detected due to organic amendments, the changes were likely more reflected to the time of sampling. This finding aligns with studies highlighting that nematode populations are sensitive to time-dependent soil factors like moisture, temperature, and organic matter decomposition rates. Any conclusion based on the treatments is therefore preliminary.
- The abundance and species richness of earthworms was overall low in the experiment. This likely relates to the coarse soil texture and yearly ploughing of the field both of which are known to reduce the growth of earthworm populations (Nieminen et al. 2011; Briones and Schmidt 2017). It is also possible that the recurrent application of pesticides had affected earthworms negatively. Two earlier studies on paper mill sludge field application on earthworms reported either positive (Pearce and Boone 1998) or negative effects (Butt et al. 2005) on earthworms. Those effects may have been due to varying indirect effects on earthworm living conditions in the prevailed experimental conditions.

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Potential drawbacks

There can always be a risk that some harmful substances end up to soil from processed starting material affecting negatively on soil biological diversity. However, we did not find indications for that. Therefore, we conclude that organic side-stream derived organic amendments in studied boreal early potato field have neutral impact on soil organisms during the three-year monitoring period.

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CASE STUDY 14a AND 14b: CONTRASTING CONTINUOUS PLANT COVER AND MINIMUM TILLAGE WITH INVERSION TILLAGE IN WHEAT FIELDS

Location

The experimental field for Case Study 14a was located in the Boreal region at Kilpiä farm in Southern Finland and for Case Study 14b in the Tyynelä farm in South-Eastern Finland (Fig. 14.1).

Fig. 14.1. Location of Case-Studies 14a and 14b.

Management practices implemented in the case study

The experiment layout for both Case Studies 14a (Fig. 14.2A) and 14b (Fig. 14.2B) followed a randomized complete block design with four replicates including a total of 8 plots. Plots with minimum tillage served as the control treatment, whereas treatment plots were mouldboard ploughed in spring before sowing in Case Study 14a or in autumn after the harvest in Case Study 14b (Fig. 14.3). Case Studies 14a and 14b field sites have been under organic farming since 2005 and 2011, and have not been ploughed since 2011 and 2017, respectively. Only minimum tillage has been conducted in both sites before the experiment start. Main crop in the cropping cycle during the 3-year monitoring time included spring wheat in Case Study 14a and winter wheat in Case Study 14b field in the first year and the third last monitoring year. There was a pea as a cover crop in both field sites in the second year. The Case Study 14a experiment started in 2020 and ended in 2022, whereas the Case Study 14b experiment was established a year later in 2021 and ended in 2023. Sampling for soil and biological diversity analyses were conducted at flag-leaf stage in the end of June or in the beginning of July, whereas sampling for earthworms was conducted in autumn.

Fig. 14.2. Experimental lay-out of Case Studies 14a (A) and 14b (B). The experimental area is organized in four blocks each divided into two plots. CTRL = minimum tillage, Plough = inversion tillage with ploughing.

Fig. 14.3. Mouldboard ploughing in Case Study 14a and minimum tillage with cultivator in Case Study 14b experimental field.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

- There was no effect of spring ploughing on prokaryotic, fungal or nematode diversity and composition. Functional 16S rRNA gene abundances were not affected by spring ploughing either.
- The abundance of 16SrRNA genes linked to C and N cycle was lower due to autumn ploughing in organic winter wheat farming, and nitrate was positively correlated with all of the genes.
- Autumn ploughing caused a decrease in nematode richness and an increase in alpha- and functional diversity. Thus, results suggest that the experimental field may be resilient for nematodes, which is beneficial for long-term soil health. However, further analysis revealed that the time of the sampling event overruled the treatment in affecting the nematode diversity. Any conclusion based on the treatments themselves is therefore preliminary.
- Earthworm communities developed under combined long-term reduced tillage and organic farming turned out to be notably resilient against the experimental deployment of ploughing.

The beneficial changes in earthworm community achieved by such management are not lost even after three consecutive years of ploughing. This appeared to be particularly so under spring ploughing, since there were indications of falling earthworm biomass under autumn ploughing. Further, under both spring and autumn ploughing the diversity of earthworms was significantly lowered in one experimental year. Both of these changes likely relate to the decrease in the abundance of deep burrowing, surface residue feeding earthworms, which is one of the most well documented biodiversity consequences of long-term application of ploughing on agricultural land (Briones and Schmidt 2017).

- It seems that occasional spring or autumn ploughing in boreal arable soils under long-term organic farming does not seem to do much harm to soil community. Occasional ploughing of boreal field under long-term organic farming may help to control dissolved P losses for several years (Uusitalo et al. 2024). Most of the earlier studies about the tillage and ploughing effects have not been investigated in real farms making comparisons difficult. Thus, cultivation history of the field is crucial factor when farming management practices are chosen.

Potential drawbacks

Based on these results spring ploughing would not cause so much harm compared to autumn ploughing. However, spring ploughing in boreal region cannot be effectively conducted in some soil types with higher content of clay or silt.

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CASE STUDY 15: USE OF CATCH CROP IN FARMED POTATO FIELDS

Location

The Case Study 15 field experiment in the Boreal region was established in Laitila, South-Western Finland, in early potato field under conventional farming (Fig. 15.1).

Fig. 15.1. Location of Case Study 15.

Management practices implemented in the case study

The experiment layout was a randomized complete block design with four replicates with a total of 12 plots, each measuring 6.5 by 32 m (Fig. 15.2). In autumn, the cover crops were not harvested but left on site. Before planting, field was ploughed, harrowed, and milled. Seed potatoes (early variety Timo) were planted (3000 kg ha^{-1}) each year in the CS15 field on mid-April and crop was harvested on mid-June. Experimental field plots had received mineral NPK fertilization (N, 44kg; P₂O₅, 18.4kg; K₂O 70.4kg), and diammonium phosphate (N 8.4kg; P₂O₅ 9.6kg) and herbicides (Proman, metobromuron 0.152kg; Fenix, aclonifen 0.168kg; Senkor, metribuzin, 0.027 kg) right after planting. Two different catch crops, phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) and rye (*Secale cereale*) were sowed in the field plots in the middle of July after the harvest in each year. Seed amount for phacelia and rye were, 15kg and 175kg ha^{-1} , respectively. Sampling for soil and biological diversity analyses were conducted in autumn.

Fig. 15.2. Experimental field and lay-out of Case Study 15. The experimental area is organized in four blocks, each divided into three plots. CTRL = control, pha= Phacelia as catch crop, rye = rye as a catch crop.

Recommended strategies to promote soil biodiversity and main benefits

The cultivation period of early potato in Finland is short, 1.5-2 months, so the soil for most of the year is bare making it prone to erosion and nutrient loss. Therefore, catch crops sowed after the harvest could prevent physical and chemical damage, nutrient and carbon loss and promote also soil biological diversity. Cover crops are known to have various beneficial effects to soil, such as a higher soil organic matter and available nutrient content, the prevention of erosion and nutrient leaching, the suppression of weeds and the control of soil-born diseases (Shennan, 1992, Wyland et al., 1996, Ritter et al., 1998, Shrestha et al., 2002).

- Overall, there was no effect of catch crops on prokaryotic, fungal or earthworm diversity and composition.
- The abundance of 16S rRNA genes linked to N cycle (degradation of urea) was lower due to the use of Phacelia as a catch crop (pha) relative to the fields where a mixture of and rye grass was employed as a catch crop (rye).
- The decline in nematode numbers with the rise in biodiversity suggests that the catch crops have improved pest and disease management. However, further analysis revealed that the timing of the sampling events had a more significant effect on nematode diversity than catch crops themselves. This outcome reinforces the impression that catch crops contributed to enhanced pest management and promoted broader ecological benefits.

- The abundance and species richness of earthworms in the field were extremely low which was likely caused by the coarse soil type and yearly ploughing and possibly also by the frequent use of pesticides. Earlier studies have shown that compared with bare fallow, catch crops can increase earthworm abundance and sometimes also their diversity (Roarty et al. 2017, Euteneuer et al. 2020). The absence of such effects in the present study may have been due to the very low initial abundance and diversity and the dependence of population growth of immigration from field margins. Qualitative observations made at the end of the experiment indicated that immigration into Phacelia treatments close to field margin would have commenced and longer duration of experiment may have led to growth of earthworm abundance and diversity.

Potential drawbacks

From the soil organism perspective, it is difficult to name any drawbacks of the used catch crops since we hardly detected any responses to them.

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